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Injection Control for Electrons in Laser-Driven Plasma Wakes on the Femtosecond Time Scale

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FOR IT IN OUR DATA.

¹ IGNORE THIS

² INCREMENT BY 2 BEFORE FOLLOWING

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MY HOBBY: FOOTNOTE LABYRINTHS

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Zusammenfassung

Lasergetriebene, plasmabasierte Beschleuniger stellen im Kiefeld des Plasmas (Wakefield) elektrische Felder zur Verfügung die um Größenordnungen höher sind als in konventionellen Beschleunigern. Um in Zukunft quasi-monoenergetische Elektronenpulse mehrere Gigaelektronenvolt zu erzeugen ist eine präzise Kontrolle auf der Skala von Femtosekunden notwendig auf welcher der Prozess der Elektroneninjektion abläuft.

In dieser Diplomarbeit wurde eine neue Methode für die externe Injektion von Elektronen in lasergetriebenen Wakefield-Beschleunigern hergeleitet. Mit der Möglichkeit relativistische, geladene Teilchenpakete mit beliebiger Verteilung in Energie, Ort und Zeit zu laden eröffnen sich neue Wege in der Untersuchung der Eigenschaften von wakefield-beschleunigten Elektronen.

Des Weiteren wurde das vorgeschlagene Schema zusammen mit einem verbesserten Gleichungslöser für die elektromagnetischen Feldgleichungen, welcher numerisches Cherenkov Rauschen unterdrückt und somit Ungenauigkeiten bei Simulationen im relativistischen Regime, in das Open Source Particle-in-Cell Programm PIconGPU implementiert.

Mit diesem ist es nun möglich, auf der Basis moderner Rechenhardware (Grafikkarten), eine neue Qualität vorhersagekräftiger, schnell wiederholbarer Simulationen zu erreichen, welche in wenigen Stunden ein Simulationsergebnis liefern im Vergleich zu bisher eingesetzten Programmen die hierfür mehrere Wochen benötigen. Neue parallele Algorithmen zur Untersuchung der Entwicklung des Beschleunigungsprozesses wurden implementiert, wie die *in-situ* Berechnung einer zweidimensionalen Phasenraumverteilung. Verzögerungsfreie Analysen wie diese führen zu einem Paradigmenwechsel für Computersimulationen hin zu interaktiven numerischen Studien und einer signifikant reduzierten Menge an Daten welche im Nachhinein ausgewertet werden müssen.

Abschließend wurden numerische Studien ausgeführt welche von den neuen Methoden und Implementierungen profitierten. Hierzu zählt ein erweitertes, auf Dichtegradienten basierendes Injektionsmodell, dass geeignet ist für die reproduzierbare Erzeugung durchstimmbarer Elektronenpakete.

Abstract

Laser-driven plasma wakefield accelerators provide accelerating electric fields orders of magnitude higher compared to conventional accelerators. Towards the generation of quasi-monoenergetic, multi-gigaelectronvolt electron beams, a precise control in the femtosecond time scale of the injection of electrons is needed.

In this diploma thesis a new computational method to study external injection of electrons in laser-wakefield accelerators was derived. By loading a relativistic, charged particle bunch with arbitrary distribution in energy, space and time new ways to study the properties of wakefield accelerated electrons are possible.

Furthermore, the proposed scheme was implemented together with an advanced field solver to suppress numerical Cherenkov noise in the open source Particle-in-Cell code PIconGPU as they are critical to reduce numerical uncertainties in relativistic simulations.

Powered with modern compute hardware (GPUs) it is now possible to reach a new quality of predictive simulations, running repeated simulations in a few hours compared to weeks as with today's legacy codes. New parallel algorithms to study the evolution of the acceleration process have been implemented such as the *in-situ* calculation of a two-dimensional phase space distribution. Providing live feedback from simulations introduces a paradigm change towards interactive numerical studies and dramatically reduces the amount of data for post-processing.

Finally, numerical studies have been carried out benefiting from the new methods and implementations such as an extended down-ramp triggered self-injection scenario suitable for the reproducible generation of tunable electron bunches.

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1 | Motivation

Plasma-based particle accelerators are a promising area of research in accelerator science. Today's conventional accelerators are usually driven by high electric fields at radio frequencies in normally or super-conducting cavities. Above 100 megavolts per meter the material's break down limit is reached as field emission of electrons from surface impurities can trigger an avalanche of secondary electrons.

As the need for compact accelerators with extremely high acceleration gradients has increased for a variety of applications in medicine and material science, alternative acceleration schemes have come into focus. One of such is plasma-based particle acceleration, aiming for a dramatic increase in the accelerating field strength using the strong electric fields from space-charge separation in a plasma excited by powerful lasers. Pioneering experiments in the field of laser-driven electron acceleration were conducted ten years ago, producing electron bunches with charges up to hundreds of picocoulomb and several hundred megaelectronvolts within few millimeters of a gas jet [1–4]. Experiments today try to reproduce, optimize, scale and stabilize these first successes to build reliable accelerators.

Recently, separating the acceleration process from the electron source using external injection has come into the focus of research as a promising way to boost energies and to control beam parameters. In order to scale to multi-gigaelectronvolts peak energies, femtosecond electron bunches must be injected and accelerated into a laser-driven wakefield with a high spatiotemporal accuracy.

From the very first prediction of laser-driven electron acceleration, computer simulations have closely accompanied experimental advances as they allow to study the plasma dynamics on the femtosecond and nanometer scale [5]. However, the widely adopted Particle-in-Cell (PIC) method up until recently

lacked an appropriate initial field solver to load relativistic, non-neutral particle bunches into a running simulation.

In this diploma thesis, new numerical models to study external electron injection in laser-driven plasma wakes are presented. A new field solver has been derived, implemented and tested, allowing for self-consistent *ab-initio* loading of charged particles of arbitrary spatial, temporal and energetic distribution into relativistic particle-in-cell simulations. This opens new paths to study the acceleration process in Laser-Wakefield Accelerators (LWFA), modeling effects like beam loading and external injection self-consistently.

Large parameter scans without simplifying assumptions are needed to provide a new quality in numerical studies. Repeated simulations with variations in initial conditions can introduce estimations for statistical errors caused by microscopic variations in the initial conditions as well as systematic errors caused by the choice of theoretical models and numerical schemes.

The PIC method, capable of performing numerical studies in the regime of highly non-linear plasma wakes, allows to resolve plasma effects that can differ orders of magnitude in size [6,7]. Consequently, a typical setup of interest demands to run several hundred thousand time steps on the largest computing facilities available today. This means that large parameter surveys or systematic studies with predictive capabilities requiring repeated simulations demand an enormous amount of computational power. Algorithms for modern compute hardware such as many-core accelerators (GPUs) can reduce computing time to a few hours for realistically sized systems and are of central importance in the presented work. Their computing power can drive exploratory numerical studies with immediate feedback from online visualization and synthetic live-analysis for researchers. This diploma thesis describes and implements state-of-the-art algorithms for the PIC method within the relativistic 3D3V code PIConGPU as well as online diagnostics.

With PIConGPU, the full set of numerical schemes for solving Maxwell's equations, solving the plasma particles' equation of motion and computing the particle currents has for the first time been implemented on the GPU architecture and provided as an open source community code. With such optimized algorithms it has now become possible to directly compare simulations to experiments for understanding and optimizing the acceleration of electrons externally injected into laser-driven wakefields on the femtosecond scale.

Figure 1.1: Visualization of the magnetic fields of a laser-wakefield accelerator (LWFA), clipped to the second period of the plasma wake. The driving laser pulse travels to the upper right of the image. The setup used a circular polarized, 30 fs long laser pulse with $a_0 = 5$, $\lambda_0 = 800$ nm and $10 \mu\text{m}$ beam waist in a hydrogen plasma of $n_e = 0.5 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. The image was created with PIconGPU (chapter 3) and ParaView [8].

1. Motivation

2 | Introduction

A simple estimation sketches the potential carried in high power lasers as drivers for particle acceleration. If one could convert laser energy directly in electron energy each Joule of the laser energy could accelerate 1 nC of electrons from rest to 1 GeV. Even if the conversion efficiency was in the per mille range, while multi-percentage theories have already been claimed [9], it is laser technology that acts as the major driver of the field.

Following the pioneering work mentioned earlier, *table-top* experiments delivered quasi-monoenergetic electron beams at 1 to 2 GeV from several cm acceleration lengths in gas [10,11]. Nevertheless, major challenges in the field of laser-electron acceleration are shot-to-shot variances. Experimental studies report a relative energy spread of 1-10 %, total energy variations around 1-5 %, a charge variation between 5-50 % and 0.5-3 mrad beam pointing which are high compared to conventional accelerators [12]. Most of these variances come from an imperfect control of the injection mechanism in the plasma that has to be mastered before building staged multi-GeV facilities [13].

New schemes with external injection and improved electron beam control require novel developments for predictable simulations. As several physical processes compete in a non-linear and sometimes self-enhancing manner, the plasma dynamics is highly complex and plainly analytical investigations are often not possible. Simulation can test (reduced) theories and scan parameter ranges for stable reproducibility. They allow to pre- and post-process data close to experiments and to study prospective setups.

The properties of plasmas discussed in this chapter help to understand important features of laser-plasma accelerators. Their fundamental properties must be modeled correctly to allow realistic, predictive numerical studies (chapter 4). Benefits and challenges of the Particle-in-Cell algorithm are presented as the main computational tool, providing the background for a

new implementation on modern hardware and the need for a new numerical method (chapter 3) to study the injection process for future experiments.

2.1 General Plasma Parameters

As defined by Chen “a plasma is a quasi-neutral gas of charged and neutral particles which exhibits collective behavior” [14]^(ch. 1). This collective behavior comes from the long-range electromagnetic interaction of charged particles. In addition to that, particles in a plasma can also interact via close collisions which will not be part of this introduction. Quasi-neutrality shall be given over a sufficiently large¹ macroscopic volume, meaning the positive and negative charges compensate each other on that scale.

2.1.1 Plasma Oscillation

How does a plasma react under a distortion and what is the minimum length scale for a plasma to be still described collectively?

Figure 2.1: Reaction of an ideal plasma upon a short excitation.

In order to answer this question one can assume a hydrogen-like pre-ionized plasma consisting of two species: positively charged ions and an adequate number of (negatively charged) electrons. If some of the electrons are displaced from their initial position the quasi-neutrality gets locally broken. An electric field will build up and result in a restoring force on the electrons. The hydrogen’s proton, as it is 1836 times heavier than the electron, can

¹see end of the section, approximately the Debye length

barely react in the same time frame as the electron. Thus only the displaced electron distribution will swing back pulled by the electric field but will obviously overshoot. That process can be approximated by a harmonic oscillation and results in the definition of the **plasma frequency** [14]^(ch. 4.3)

$$\omega_{pe} = \sqrt{\frac{n_e e^2}{m_e \epsilon_0}} \quad (2.1)$$

for $m_e \ll m_i$ and quasi infinite plasmas. The derivation of this formula is done for the 1D case in [14]^(ch. 4.3) which is a good approximation for radially symmetric problems. The electrostatic oscillation of the electrons can be described by the corresponding equation of motion

$$m_e n_e \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_e}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v}_e \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}_e \right] = - e n_e \mathbf{E} \quad (2.2)$$

and has to satisfy the continuity equation

$$\frac{\partial n_e}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_e \mathbf{v}_e) = 0 \quad . \quad (2.3)$$

Eventually, one can already draw a first conclusion out of that simplified formula (2.1). The group velocity $v_g = \partial\omega/\partial k$ vanishes because ω_{pe} does not depend on k . That means a plasma oscillation does not propagate like, e.g., the water waves on the surface of a pool would do after throwing a stone in it.

2.1.2 Cold and Collisionless Plasmas

Realistic plasmas can hold a collective electron temperature. On the one hand a temperature will allow oscillations in the plasma to propagate due to thermal motion. On the other hand it will also prevent the plasma to react upon an arbitrarily large charge difference in the plasma with a perfect, infinitely small layer of screening electrons. One expects that the charged particles will rearrange around the source of an electric field while screening it efficiently over a distinct half-length.

Defining the **Debye length** quantifies this effect [14]^(ch. 1.4)

Figure 2.2: Example of an anode in a pre-ionized plasma and screening effect. The rearrangement of nearby charges shields the influence a local charge imbalance causes upon a plasma.

$$\lambda_D = \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon_0 k_B T_e}{n_e e^2}} . \quad (2.4)$$

As the equation of motion (2.2) can be extended by adding a temperature term $-3k_B T_e \partial n_e / \partial x$ on the right-hand side, the derived dispersion relation changes to [14]^(ch. 4.4)

$$\omega^2 = \omega_{pe}^2 + 3/2 \mathbf{k}^2 v_{th}^2 \quad (2.5)$$

with $v_{th} = \sqrt{2k_B T / m_e}$ for a Maxwellian velocity distribution. Figure 2.3 illustrates (2.5) that a local excitation propagates in a warm plasma, since the group velocity is non-zero [14]^(ch. 4.4).

One can define the so called **Debye Sphere** as the volume with radius λ_D outside which charges are efficiently screened. The number of electrons within such a sphere is usually called the Debye number $N_D = 4/3\pi n_e \lambda_D^3$.

The influence of elastic, binary Coulomb collisions can be approximated via the **plasma coupling parameter** $\Gamma_p = E_c / k_B T_e$ as the ratio between Coulomb energy and thermal energy. One discriminates strongly ($\Gamma_p \gg 1$) from weakly ($\Gamma_p \ll 1$) coupled plasmas. The latter describes a densely populated Debye Sphere where collective interactions with the background fields dominate.

In conclusion, if one wants to describe the collective, statistical electromag-

Figure 2.3: Bohm-Gross dispersion relation (2.5) for Langmuir waves in a warm plasma [14]^(fig. 4.5). For high k the phase and group velocity converge to $\sqrt{3/2} \cdot v_{th}$.

netic behavior of a plasma the coupling parameter should be $\Gamma_p \ll 1$, the considered length scale should be at least of the order of the Debye length λ_D and the corresponding time scale should be on scales of the plasma period [14]^(ch. 1.5f).

For the regime of Laser-Wakefield Accelerators (introduced in section 2.2) and its according models in Particle-in-Cell simulations binary collisions are negligible. The simulations performed in this diploma thesis are not bound to the approximations of collective plasmas and can generate their collective properties from the underlying kinetic effects on a significantly smaller scale (motivation and method in section 2.3).

2.1.3 Electromagnetic Waves in Plasmas

Plasmas of charged particles interact via electromagnetic fields. Starting with the definition of the plasma frequency (2.1) it follows that a plasma reacts within a distinct time in the order of ω_{pe}^{-1} upon an excitation.

Let this excitation be an electric wave with frequency ω_0 . The plasma will

2. Introduction

barely have enough time to react upon the oscillating electromagnetic field if the wave's frequency is much higher than the plasma frequency ω_{pe} . Therefore the electromagnetic wave is able to penetrate and propagate in the plasma. As ω_0 is reduced closer to the scale of ω_{pe} the electrons in the plasma start to resonate. By that they create an electric current that will by Faraday's Law absorb energy from the immanent wave. Eventually the speed at which certain wave numbers can propagate will depend on the ratio between both of these frequencies [14]^(ch. 4.12)

$$\omega_0^2 = \omega_{pe}^2 + c^2 k_0^2 \quad . \quad (2.6)$$

Qualitatively this result for electromagnetic waves is very close to what one obtains for the dispersion relation of plasma waves in figure 2.3. The main difference is that the maximum gradient of $\omega_0(k_0)$ is given by the vacuum speed of light.

For $\omega_0 = \omega_{pe}$ the critical density n_c can be derived from (2.1). The plasma's electrons can react so fast to the oscillations of the electromagnetic wave that it cannot propagate any more. That divides plasmas for a distinct electromagnetic wave length into over-dense ($n_e > n_c$) and under-dense (transparent, $n_e < n_c$) plasmas

$$n_c = m_e \epsilon_0 \omega_0^2 e^{-2} \quad . \quad (2.7)$$

From the dispersion relation (2.6) follows that the phase velocity $v_\phi = \omega_0/k_0 = \sqrt{c^2 + \omega_{pe}^2/k_0^2}$ can exceed the vacuum speed of light c . At the same time the group velocity stays at $v_g = c^2/v_\phi$. Consequently, a plasma is a state of matter where the refractive index

$$n(k_0) = \frac{c}{v_\phi} = \frac{ck_0}{\omega(k_0)} = \sqrt{\epsilon\mu} \quad (2.8)$$

is less than 1. Also the dielectric permittivity

$$\epsilon = 1 - \frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{\omega^2} \quad (2.9)$$

is less than unity for under-dense plasmas. Equation (2.8) leads to an exponentially attenuated solution for over-dense plasmas because the refractive index n is imaginary in that regime.

2.2 Laser-Wakefield Acceleration

As discussed in the last section, electromagnetic waves can propagate in an under-dense plasma. The special case of a high-intensity ($\gtrsim 10^{17}$ W/cm²) electromagnetic pulse that is finite in space and time is considered. For a pulse length and waist in the order of a plasma wavelength λ_p a laser pulse is powerful and short enough to drive a plasma wave, creating a trailing wakefield (figure 2.4) [15].

At the time of the proposal of the Laser-Wakefield Acceleration/Accelerator (LWFA), ultra-short ($\lesssim 1$ ps) laser pulses with adequate intensities were not yet available and alternative schemes such as the self-modulated (SM-LWFA) and the plasma beat wave accelerator (PBWA) were prospected to enhance the driver [5]. The invention of *table-top* terrawatt laser systems powered by chirped pulse amplification (CPA) in the mid-1980s changed the scientific field significantly, providing the ultra-short high-power laser pulses considered in this diploma thesis [16].

Figure 2.4: Scheme for LWFA in the blowout regime. The ponderomotive force along the envelope’s gradient of a short laser pulse acts as the driving force of the process. The “bubble” behind the driver is nearly evacuated from electrons, building a homogeneously charged cavity from the ion background. Image created with PIConGPU (see section 3.1).

One can define the ponderomotive force [14]^(ch. 8.4) as the effective non-linear force that results from the averaged intensity gradient in a laser driver:

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{NL}} = -\frac{\omega_{pe}^2}{\omega_0^2} \nabla \left\langle \frac{\epsilon_0 \mathbf{E}^2}{2} \right\rangle . \quad (2.10)$$

Defining the normalized vector potential \mathbf{a} [15] one characterizes the peak amplitude of a pulse by the laser strength parameter a_0

$$\mathbf{a} = \frac{e\mathbf{A}}{m_e c^2} \simeq \frac{e\mathbf{E}_{\text{Lin}}}{\omega_0 m_e c} \quad (2.11)$$

$$\text{Gaussian profile: } I_0 = \frac{\pi c}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{m_e c^2 a_0}{e \lambda_0} \right)^2 . \quad (2.12)$$

The definition of the laser strength parameter can be motivated regarding the acceleration felt by an electron within the first half-wave of an incident electromagnetic wave. Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_{\text{Lin}} &= E(t) = E_0 \cdot \sin(\omega_0 t) \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} &= e \cdot E(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

By separation of variables it yields

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{p_{\text{max}}} dp &= \int_0^{\pi/\omega_0} e \cdot E(t) dt \\ \Leftrightarrow p_{\text{max}} &= e \cdot E_0 \cdot \frac{2}{\omega_0} \end{aligned} .$$

An electron reaches roughly a relativistic momentum within the first half-wave of the (peak) electric wave for

$$\begin{aligned} m_e \cdot c \leq p_{\text{max}} &= e \cdot E_0 \cdot \frac{2}{\omega_0} \\ \Rightarrow 1 \leq 2 \frac{e \cdot E_0}{\omega_0 m_e c} &= 2 \cdot a_0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.14)$$

which leads to the convention to divide into intensities $a_0 > 1$ where relativistic effects of the plasma become relevant and the non-relativistic regime $a_0 < 1$.

The choice of the laser strength parameter a_0 leads to a qualitative change in the plasma dynamics. Linear plasma wakes driven by low-intensity ($a_0 < 1$)

Figure 2.5: Linear and non-linear wake fields for a variation of the laser strength parameter from a_0 ($\lambda_0 = 800$ nm, $\tau = 30$ fs, $w_0 = 10$ μ m, circular polarized, $n_e = 0.5 \cdot 10^{19}$ cm $^{-3}$). The 3D study was carried out with a newly developed *in-situ* analysis in PIConGPU (section 3.2) and IPython [17].

laser pulses can still be described analytically with hydrodynamic, cold fluid models. Whereas the kinetic effects in the relativistic regime for $a_0 > 1$ result in a highly non-linear dynamics requiring kinetic simulations for a full description.

The study in figure 2.5 shows the response of a pre-ionized hydrogen plasma by varying the laser strength parameter of the incident laser pulse. The non-relativistic regime, represented by figure 2.5a, can be described by an electron density wave that follows the laser driver. Some of the electrons are expelled from their initial position in the gas and swing back as the laser has passed. By overshooting they create a longitudinal wake whose phase is locked to the laser driver.

As the laser intensity rises the wave approximation fails (figure 2.5b) and wave breaking can occur [7]. In wave breaking, some electrons can *surf down* the electric potential build up by the plasma wave and overtake other electrons at the same position. This effect is kinetic and can not be approximated by a fluid-like assumption of a discrete velocity value per discrete volume. Later on, this will motivate the use of the Particle-in-Cell (PIC) method for

simulations (section 2.3).

The projection of the longitudinal phase space is convenient for the dynamics of an accelerator as the accelerating electric fields are strongest along the axis of propagation. Nevertheless, a full description of a plasma accelerator must consider the evolution of the full six-dimensional phase space (3D3V) in time. For entirely electromagnetic forces the phase space distribution function $f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$ is given by the **Vlasov equation** [14]^(ch. 7.2). Derived from the collisionless Boltzmann equation it yields

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f + \frac{q}{m} (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = 0 \quad . \quad (2.15)$$

As discussed in a following section, the PIC method can be interpreted as a linear test-particle method conserving (2.15).

The effects in figure 2.5b are characteristic for the blowout regime [7]. Above the threshold of either the laser intensity

$$\frac{a_0^2}{\sqrt{1+a_0}} \geq k_{pe}^2 w_0^2 / 4 \quad (2.16)$$

with the laser spot size w_0 or, alternatively, $w_0 \leq 2\sqrt{a_0}/k_{pe}$ the volume behind the driver is nearly evacuated from electrons and can be approximated by a homogenous, positively charged sphere of resting ions [15]. The following section will derive some characteristic parameters for the LWFA in this regime.

2.2.1 Characteristic Length Scales for Wakefield Acceleration

In under-dense plasmas the laser's group velocity is given by

$$v_{0,g} = c\sqrt{1 - \omega_p^2/\omega_0^2} \quad (2.17)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \gamma_{0,g} = \gamma_0 = \omega_0/\omega_p \quad . \quad (2.18)$$

For a constant density profile one can assume that the group velocity of the driver is the same as the phase velocity of the plasma.

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Electron density oscillations in the wake are in first order approximated by a harmonic oscillation with frequency ω_{pe} . The wave length of the wake follows as $\lambda_{pe} = v_{0,g} \cdot 2\pi/\omega_{pe}$. In the highly relativistic regime this leads approximately to the size of an ion bubble (the first half-period of the wake) of $\lambda_{pe}/2$.

The laser pulse in an LWFA transfers energy to the background plasma by constantly expelling electrons from it. By that it loses energy over time causing depletion [15, 18, 19]. That happens over a length of:

$$L_{\text{depletion}}(\lambda_0, \lambda_{pe}, a_0) \simeq \frac{\lambda_{pe}^3}{\lambda_0^2} \begin{cases} \sqrt{2}a_0/\pi & : a_0 \gg 1 \\ 2/a_0^2 & : a_0 \ll 1 \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

As one of the constraints for an LWFA experiment, the influence of the **laser depletion length** (2.19) on the accessible electron densities for selected high-power laser systems is illustrated in figure 2.6. Further parameters that have to be considered follow below.

Figure 2.6: Upper limit for accessible electron densities to excite wake fields in terms of laser depletion (2.19). Reference areas shown for the high power lasers at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden - Rossendorf (HZDR). Rationale: if particles are injected in the wake for LWFA experiments, further restrictions as the finite Rayleigh length of the laser beam have to be taken into account. Dynamic effects like particle dephasing or beam loading require to use even lower densities.

Let a highly relativistic test particle ($v \simeq c$) be set at the end of the first half-period of the plasma wake. The movement of the accelerating structure is limited by the group velocity $\gamma_{0,g}$ of the laser. At some point the particle catches up the first half-wave of the bubble, as seen in figure 2.7 for E_y , and will from that point be decelerated again. One calls this characteristic length, that can be utilized for acceleration of injected electron bunches, the **dephasing length** [15]

$$L_{\text{dephasing}}(\lambda_0, \lambda_{\text{pe}}, a_0) \simeq \frac{\lambda_{\text{pe}}^3}{2\lambda_0^2} \begin{cases} \sqrt{2}a_0/\pi N_p & : a_0 \gg 1 \\ 1 & : a_0 \ll 1 \end{cases} \quad (2.20)$$

$$\xrightarrow{a_0 \gg 1} L_{\text{dephasing}} = L_{\text{depletion}} \cdot \frac{1}{2N_p} \quad (2.21)$$

with N_p being the number of plasma periods behind the driving pulse.

When a diffraction-limited laser pulse is focused to a beam waist w_0 a distinct relation between its central wavelength λ_0 , w_0 and the *Rayleigh length* z_R yields (in the paraxial approximation)

$$z_R = \frac{\pi w_0^2}{\lambda_0} \quad . \quad (2.22)$$

z_R characterizes the distance along the beam's direction of propagation on which its cross-section doubles. In experiments this length is defined by the focal distance of the final parabolic mirror focusing the beam to the target. As the intensity of the laser pulse drops rapidly with z_R , its defocusing restricts the maximum acceleration length, too.

In addition to that, laser pulses with a finite beam waist create a radial ponderomotive force (2.10). This force lowers the plasma electron density that the main part of the laser pulse passes through, expelling electrons from areas of high laser intensity, thereby reducing the plasma frequency closer to the laser's axis of propagation. Above the critical power [15]

$$P_c \simeq 17.4 \text{ GW} \cdot \left(\frac{\omega_0}{\omega_{\text{pe}}} \right)^2$$

the pulse is consequently focused by the plasma that is acting as a con-

vex lens [14]^(ch. 8.4). It is worth mentioning that the minimum focus is still diffraction-limited preventing infinite focusing. An optimal or “matched” focal spot size for $P = P_c$ can lead to a beam guiding over long distances at the vacuum minimum beam waist w_0 . Deviations from this focusing can even lead to a slow oscillation of the transverse envelope alternating between **self-focusing** and diffraction.

A comparison of the effects in this section with typical lengths between mm to cm and the underlying plasma processes on the order of the plasma wavelength λ_{pe} highlights the orders of magnitude a simulation has to connect in time and space. The following chapters (see 2.3, 3) will explain how new algorithms on modern compute hardware can be harnessed to simulate whole acceleration scenarios from the fundamental interactions on the microscopic scale in very short time with online feedback.

2.2.2 Accelerating and Focusing Fields

In the blowout regime the form of the electron cavity behind the driver approximately resembles a homogenous sphere of background ions. Electrons that are injected in that cavity will undergo an acceleration as long as they do not cross the center plane of the sphere. Neglecting space charge effects of the injected particles, the accelerating fields can therefore be approximated as linearly decreasing towards the center (figure 2.7).

Figure 2.7: Visualization of the accelerating and focusing electric fields in the plasma wakefield (laser running to the bottom). The image was clipped to the second period of the wake to neglect the influence of the primary laser fields. Images created with PIconGPU (section 3.1) and IPython [17].

Transversal electric fields in the bubble lead to a strong focusing of the injected charge and can lead to betatron oscillations. In turn betatron oscillations of relativistic electrons are promising sources of X-ray radiation [20,21]. A challenge for simulations is not to overestimate the interaction of injected charges with residues of the driving laser in the bubble which can lead to an overestimation of the potential betatron oscillation in polarization direction [22]. Higher-order numerical schemes can reduce the error, but require more computational power (compare to section 2.3 and chapter 3).

The strong return currents in the sheet of electrons forming the bubble create intense magnetic fields (see figure 1.1). These act as an additional focusing force on electrons traveling in the cavity as the current of the injected electrons and the outer sheet are anti-parallel. At the same time injected charges can deform (widen) the bubble due to their space charge which is known as *beam loading* [23].

As seen in figure 2.7, the accelerating structures for plasma-based laser-electron acceleration are well known. The challenge is therefore to control the properties of the injected electron bunch resulting from its injection dynamics into these micrometer large accelerating fields.

2.3 Particle-in-Cell Simulations

Particle-in-Cell (PIC) simulations accompany the field of laser-particle acceleration from the very beginning [5]. As introduced in the previous sections, simulations have to reproduce processes differing orders of magnitude in time and space to create a full picture of the fundamental interactions in an LWFA.

For under-dense plasmas the smallest wave length to resolve is the central wave length of the laser $\lambda_0 \lesssim 1 \mu\text{m}$ longitudinally,² usually sampled with 25 or more grid points (see section 2.3.1). The plasma skin depth c/ω_{pe} should be resolved by at least 10 grid points - limiting the maximum cell size in transversal direction. The resulting time scale for simulation steps is $\lambda_0/c \simeq \mathcal{O}(\text{fs})$. In the blowout regime the size of each bubble spans a few λ_{pe} and its evolution should be followed over the full dephasing length of several millimeters or tens of picoseconds, respectively. Simulation setups can require several trillion supporting points in space and have to be developed over hundred of thousands of time steps (examples in chapter 4).

The PIC algorithm bases on very few assumptions. The resulting high applicability comes with higher computational costs compared to, e.g., fluid approaches like in magneto-hydro-dynamics (MHD). Since basic kinetic features as the Larmor radius or the plasma frequency have to be resolved in space and time, the PIC algorithm is a very general but relatively resource-intensive algorithm, compared to the foremost mentioned algorithms that usually approximate these effects by averaging.

Implementations on modern hardware like Graphics Processing Units (GPU) address this need (section 3.1). Together with live analysis running in parallel to the simulation (sections 3.1.2, 3.2) it is possible to advance theoretical models and to follow complex dynamics in the acceleration mechanism.

The PIC algorithm is a particle mesh method which divides data in two domains: spatial discrete grid points and finite particles between them.³ Electromagnetic fields are distributed in space on the mentioned grid points, usually with equidistant spacing for each component.

²Most high-power short-pulse laser systems operate in the near-infrared range, e.g., Ti:Sapphire lasers around 800 nm.

³As described later in detail, this indicates it is not *per se* well fitted for advanced compute hardware since these two domains require at least some sorting to interact (section 3.1).

Figure 2.8: The explicit PIC cycle, advancing the simulation for one time step Δt .

Figure 2.8 illustrates the full PIC cycle as it is explained in the following sections in detail. In addition to solving the rotation terms in Maxwell's equations one self-consistently adds test-particles that interact with the finite spatial domain. In contrast to the discretized electromagnetic fields the particles are sampled continuously in space and a multiple of these macro particles can exist within a field-wise linearized simulation volume called a cell.

2.3.1 Solving Maxwells Equations

In order to find an efficient solver to simulate the propagation of electromagnetic waves from antennas, K. Yee [24] proposed a finite-difference time-domain (FDTD) scheme to solve the set of partial differential Maxwell equations in isotropic media

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \quad (2.23)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad (2.24)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad (2.25)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \mu_0 \epsilon_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \quad (2.26)$$

Electromagnetic fields are stacked in time and space using stencil operations (finite differences) to explicitly advance both (see figure 2.9).

This defines a second order solver:

$$\Delta \mathbf{E}_{ijk}^n = \nabla^{(-)} \times \mathbf{B}^{n-\frac{1}{2}} \cdot \frac{\Delta t}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0} \quad (2.27)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^{(-)} \times \mathbf{B} &= \left(\frac{B_{z,ijk} - B_{z,ij-1k}}{\Delta y} - \frac{B_{y,ijk} - B_{y,ijk-1}}{\Delta z} \right) \mathbf{e}_x \\ &+ \left(\frac{B_{x,ijk} - B_{x,ijk-1}}{\Delta z} - \frac{B_{z,ijk} - B_{z,i-1jk}}{\Delta x} \right) \mathbf{e}_y \\ &+ \left(\frac{B_{y,ijk} - B_{y,i-1jk}}{\Delta x} - \frac{B_{x,ijk} - B_{x,ij-1k}}{\Delta y} \right) \mathbf{e}_z \end{aligned}$$

$$\Delta \mathbf{B}_{ijk}^{n+\frac{1}{2}} = -\nabla^{(+)} \times \mathbf{E}^n \cdot \Delta t \quad (2.28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^{(+)} \times \mathbf{E} &= \left(\frac{E_{z,ij+1k} - E_{z,ijk}}{\Delta y} - \frac{E_{y,ijk+1} - E_{y,ijk}}{\Delta z} \right) \mathbf{e}_x \\ &+ \left(\frac{E_{x,ijk+1} - E_{x,ijk}}{\Delta z} - \frac{E_{z,i+1jk} - E_{z,ijk}}{\Delta x} \right) \mathbf{e}_y \\ &+ \left(\frac{E_{y,i+1jk} - E_{y,ijk}}{\Delta x} - \frac{E_{x,ij+1k} - E_{x,ijk}}{\Delta y} \right) \mathbf{e}_z \end{aligned}$$

The required operations are only local, computing the rotational terms (2.25), (2.26) and neglecting source terms like \mathbf{J} and ρ . The convergence criterion for this set of equations is called the Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy (CFL) [25] criterion which is limiting the ratio of time step to cell size.^{4,5} Since the electric and magnetic Gaussian equations are not considered by the algorithm, both are only conserved as long as the initial and boundary conditions are matched correctly.

Figure 2.9: Spatial and temporal distribution of the individual components of the electromagnetic field in Yee's scheme.

⁴Rationale: within one time step an electromagnetic wave can travel up to one cell.

⁵The original Yee-CFL criterion was derived too conservative and corrected in [26].

At this point all four of Maxwell's equations for isotropic media are conserved over time with second order accuracy. A straight forward expansion can now incorporate dielectric and polarized background media by introducing the appropriate tensors for ϵ and μ in the rotational terms.⁶

Since the discretized curls in the Yee scheme are correct to second order any derived linear operators such as a Laplacian feature errors growing slower than the square of the time step. Thus, the wave equation is satisfied up to second order:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{u}}{\partial t^2} &= c^2 \cdot \nabla^2 \mathbf{u} \\
 \text{Yee for } \mathbf{E} &\Leftrightarrow \nabla^2 = \nabla(-) \cdot \nabla(+) \\
 c^{-2} \cdot \frac{\mathbf{E}_{ijk}^{n-1} - 2\mathbf{E}_{ijk}^n + \mathbf{E}_{ijk}^{n+1}}{(\Delta t)^2} &= \frac{E_{x,i-1jk}^n - 2E_{x,ijk}^n + E_{x,i+1jk}^n}{(\Delta x)^2} \cdot \mathbf{e}_x \\
 &+ \frac{E_{y,ij-1k}^n - 2E_{y,ijk}^n + E_{y,ij+1k}^n}{(\Delta y)^2} \cdot \mathbf{e}_y \\
 &+ \frac{E_{z,ijk-1}^n - 2E_{z,ijk}^n + E_{z,ijk+1}^n}{(\Delta z)^2} \cdot \mathbf{e}_z \quad (2.29)
 \end{aligned}$$

with c being the speed of light in the medium. It follows directly from the discretization of the electromagnetic fields that wave numbers smaller than the Nyquist limit $k = \pi/\Delta x$ cannot be sampled.

Numerical Dispersion

This is not the only constraint on wavelengths resolved by simulations. For LWFA the correct modeling for the dispersion of a driving laser pulse is important as it has been shown that a chirped laser⁷ changes the dynamic evolution and injection process [28, 29]. In appendix A the numerical dispersion relation $\omega(k)$ for Yee's scheme is derived which yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\sin(\omega\Delta t/2)}{c\Delta t} &= \frac{\sin(k_x\Delta x/2)}{\Delta r} \\
 v_{\text{group}}(k) = \frac{\partial\omega}{\partial k} & \quad v_{\phi}(k) = \frac{\omega}{k} \quad .
 \end{aligned}$$

⁶Combined with particles from section 2.3.2 exotic states of matter like meta-materials can be modeled [27].

⁷a laser with an (intentionally) shifted central frequency over time and/or space

Figure 2.10: Numerical group and phase velocity (7), (10) in the one-dimensional Yee scheme. Staying close to the CFL criterion is essential to minimize numerical artifacts. In 2 and 3D simulations, waves propagating along the diagonal of the cells with Δt set to the CFL limit are modeled dispersion-free, too.

Except for long wave lengths the physically correct relation $\omega^2 = c^2 \cdot \mathbf{k}^2 \forall \mathbf{k}$ is only represented correctly in the limit of infinitesimal time steps and cells: $\Delta t \ll 1, \Delta x \ll 1$. The choice of a time step close to the CFL criterion can at least minimize the effect as seen in figure 2.10.

The propagation of relativistic particles is not bound to the same purely numerical speed limit. It has been shown in recent publications [30] that exactly the particles that are overcoming the artificially lowered phase velocity v_ϕ in figure 2.10 happen to emit numerical Cherenkov noise in the under-sampled high frequencies.

This in turn leads to one of the main challenges today in PIC simulations: the control of artificial plasma instabilities in fast moving plasma slabs (relevant for so called boosted-frame simulations [31]) and the correct prediction of emittance for accelerated, charged bunches. In LWFA this mainly blurs the properties of injected electrons, their total charge and transverse emittance, which are usually overestimated due to these effects. The first implementation of the full PIC cycle on GPUs (chapter 3) provides the potential to increase the resolution and to compute advanced, high-order schemes in less time to approach these challenges.

Eventually, by changing the Yee stencil to a higher order and thereby manipulating the numerical dispersion relation can reduce numerical artifacts. Nevertheless, state-of-the-art solvers [30, 32–35] still hold the issues of either triggering new numerical instabilities, only conserving the dispersion

relation in specific directions for a fixed time step or being restricted to quadratic/cubic cells.

2.3.2 Grid-Particle Interactions

The previously described field solver of the PIC method did not incorporate particle densities. It is in principle possible to introduce a hydrodynamic model by just adding a density and velocity value per grid point. However the PIC algorithm chooses a specific Particle-Mesh (PM) model that will be the topic of this section.

First of all the limit of fluid models is overcome by allowing multiple velocity components per finite cell volume by introducing particles with continuous positions in the cells (figure 2.11).

Figure 2.11: Spatially continuous distribution of particles in a discrete grid of the cells.

Already at this point one can see that this allows to simulate processes like crossing trajectories in wave breaking (section 2.2). One can now assign arbitrary attributes to particles with the most important ones being position, momentum and the electric charge to mass ratio. An additional important attribute, the particle weighting, will be discussed later.

Staying a bit longer with the attribute *position* one demands that it only characterizes the center of the particle. The particle (and therefore its charge, mass, etc.) is given a finite size described by the cloud shape.⁸ Since the key attribute for force calculation and summing up the currents in Maxwell's equations is the density that all particles contribute to a single cell one usually only speaks about the integral of the cloud shape, the so called

⁸Point-like particles cause a strong *ringing* when crossing a cell boundary since they deposit their full charge abruptly.

2. Introduction

assignment function⁹ (examples in figure 2.12). Its evaluation at a point reveals immediately the mass/charge part a particle deploys in a cell. This assignment function is usually build up from s convolutions¹⁰ with a box function [37]^(ch. 5).

Figure 2.12: First and second order charge profiles of particles are assigned to the according cells to weight particle-mesh interactions. The hatched sections can be evaluated from the pre-integrated assignment function at discrete grid points.

Since particles interact with the fields on the grid an interpolation is necessary to calculate the Lorentz force.¹¹ The association of grid and particles requires sorting adapted data structures as introduced in section 3.1 to profit from vectorized hardware like GPUs.

Force Weighting and Particle Push

By summing up the fields of cells a particle contributes to, taking in account the particle’s shape function, one can interpolate the fields acting on a particle. Even if this does not represent the change in momentum $\partial_t p$, the literature calls this algorithm “force weighting” [36]^(ch. 2). The change in momentum (*particle push*) designates the force action on a particle caused by the electric field \mathbf{E} and magnetic field \mathbf{B} , which are usually not defined at the same point in time and space (figure 2.9). Popular schemes for the particle push were proposed by Boris [38] and Vay [39].

One can manipulate $\partial_t p$ even more by adding additional inner forces. In this case the right-hand side of the Vlasov equation (2.15) is non-zero, including collisions it yields

⁹Also known as the assignment (function) shape, often simply referred to as *shape*.

¹⁰A point-like particle would be represented by $s = 0$. Higher order shape functions are known to reduce unphysical effects and stochastic noise in simulations [36]^(ch. 2).

¹¹That itself is challenging as higher-order shapes require caching (or pre-fetching) on modern hardware to exploit high-bandwidth, local memory efficiently.

$$\left(\frac{df}{dt}\right) = \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial t}\right)_{\text{collisions}} . \quad (2.30)$$

This causes particles to interact *directly* with each other, allowing to expand the basic PIC algorithm to a Particle-Particle-Particle-Mesh (P³M) method. Moreover, non-classical effects like radiation damping and photon emission would modify the change in momentum at this point in the algorithm.

Similar to the electromagnetic field components \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{B} the momentum and position are stored with half a time step difference. Finally the leapfrog propagation of the particle is performed in a linearized movement with the new momentum for the time step Δt . The system's conservation of momentum is guaranteed by treating all grid points equally (limited translation invariance) and by using an on-axis left-right symmetry of the particles' shape [36]^(ch. 8).

Current Deposition

Interpreting the particle movement as an extension to the field solver leads to the consequence that both have to be coupled self-consistently. The first part, the influence of the fields on the charged particles, has been added already. The back-reaction has to be performed accordingly since moving, charged particles create a current and that current again modifies the electric field via Ampère's law

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{E}}{\Delta t} = -c^2 \mu_0 \mathbf{J} . \quad (2.31)$$

A widely adopted paper by Esirkepov [40] derives a general current deposition scheme for a large class of particle shapes. The important point is that one can avoid solving a Poisson equation for the moving particles by conserving the (numerical) continuity equation at the same time as the divergence of the magnetic field

$$\nabla^{(\mathbf{E})} \cdot \mathbf{J} = -\frac{\Delta \rho}{\Delta t} \quad (2.32)$$

$$\nabla^{(\mathbf{B})} \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 . \quad (2.33)$$

If both are met the charge conservation via $\nabla^{(\mathbf{E})} \cdot \mathbf{E} = \rho/\epsilon_0$ follows self-consistently.

Macro Particles and Weighting

Finally particles shall be interpreted a bit more. Binning them into a phase space image reveals that each particle has a certain width in space caused by the finite assignment function. That is not the case in momentum direction since each particle has only one momentum attribute. Per particle, the simulation advances a rigid cloud without rotational or vibrational motion. Two particles can also pass each other freely.

But what does *one particle* represent? A single electron, partly to fully charged ion or atom? Since the computational demand would grow unreasonably fast in such a case,¹² one groups several hundred *real* particles with a distinct weighting into a so called **macro particle**. Consequently, a simulated particle represents the averaged micro-dynamics of multiple particles, neglecting inner forces.

On the one side *under-weighting*, simulating less than a few dozen particles or even less than one particle with a macro particle, will not lead to trustworthy results. One would basically create classical, sub-elementary particles in such a case which is, e.g., for electrons unjustifiable regarding results from experiments.

On the other side *over-weighting* to save simulation time can cause serious numerical noise as forces and currents are modeled more roughly. Regarding the distribution of momenta again, more particles should in principle allow to fill the local phase space within a few cells more evenly, building the sampling points in momentum. For accelerator science the region of interest is the evolution of the full 6D phase space (2.15) and missing supporting points in three of these dimensions can make the difference between a promising injection scheme for LWFA and a numerical artifact. Adequate weighting and thus an increased number of macro particles per cell can have a positive impact on investigations of certain plasma phenomena¹³ and effects on the scale of a few cells.

¹²And a single quantum object is microscopically not well described solely by electro-dynamics.

¹³For example, the growth rate of a plasma instability growing ab-initio from a temperature seed.

Features of the PIC Cycle related to LWFA

This diploma thesis adds a new algorithm complementing the fully relativistic, electromagnetic PIC cycle (section 3.3). At no point in it a Poisson equation is solved, leading to the consequence that the divergence terms of Maxwell's equations, when respected in starting and boundary conditions, should only be maintained by the self-consistency of the PIC algorithm. What does that mean for a simulation where only electron macro particles are initialized, field-free, without compensating ions? An external force, e.g. a laser pulse, displaces the electrons and the electric current they cause builds up electromagnetic fields. These fields will eventually look as if there was an ion in the background that is still sitting at the initial position with infinite mass. If the disturbance is finite in time the electrons will react on these fields and oscillate around their original positions.

Usually, LWFA in under-dense plasmas can be modeled quite precisely by neglecting the long-term ion dynamics. Moreover, the ionization dynamics are quasi-instantaneous for strong laser pulses and low- Z gases, which motivates to initialize a pre-ionized target plasma. Since all particles can be removed from a simulation that will not react with the grid by causing currents, being ionized or similar, one can initialize the electrons of the gas only.

Nevertheless, if one wants to simulate a charged particle bunch with correct initial fields that problem of space charge becomes non-trivial. For plasma-based accelerators such as the Plasma-Wakefield Acceleration/Accelerator (PWFA) correct initial conditions for the driving beam are utterly important. The study of injection dynamics in LWFA requires to load external electron beams correctly to discriminate the injection and acceleration process for stable acceleration mechanisms. Section 3.3 will introduce a general solution for that and will furthermore implement it on advanced compute hardware.

2.4 Injection Control Schemes

In most plasma-based accelerators today the source of to-be-accelerated particles *overlaps* (in time or space) with the geometry of the accelerator itself. Therefore, the processes of injection and acceleration are hard to divide in studies. Ideal concepts would separate both processes strictly, as in conventional particle accelerators.

The goal of advanced injection control schemes is to improve the overall beam quality and stability. Applications need high bunch charges in a very short time at high and narrow peak energy while beam transport requires a low emittance and stable pointing [12].

2.4.1 Scaling Limits of Self-Injection

Electron injection from the background plasma, most prominent in the self-injection due to wave breaking, is a well-know mechanism in LWFA [6, 7]. This process is triggered above a critical laser power P_c [41], injecting background electrons from the plasma in the cavity behind the laser. Related methods using transitions in the density gradient are trapping electrons as the bubble expands which happens due to the increase in the plasma wavelength λ_{pe} that defines the bubble-radius.

Neither the power of the laser nor the density of the gas profile can be changed rapidly to turn the process of self-injection on and off. The injection occurs over a relatively long time which increases the acceleration length and energy spread of injected background electrons. Even scaling to a very high trapped charge is not trivial as the bubble has to *collect* background charge at the same time as earlier injected charge is already accelerated, potentially reaching the dephasing length during this collection process (see chapter 2.2.2).

In section 4.2 of this diploma thesis a typical scenario in this regime is carried out. Using high resolution simulations on modern hardware allows to study that regime over several millimeters of gas jets that can potentially be used to create highly charged bunches with a fixed energy-time relation for which improvements in emittance can be expected. Nevertheless, the production of extremely short and monoenergetic electron beams is challenging with this method.

2.4.2 Overview of Alternative Mechanisms

The limits of self-injection were recognized early and several alternative schemes have been proposed. The LWFA accelerates charged particles as soon as they reside within the separatrix of the wakefield, preferably the first bubble as it carries the strongest fields. It is therefore convenient to distinguish between methods that (temporarily) deform the separatrix to trap particles and methods that *push* or create electrons into the separatrix. As mentioned for self-injection, the chronological sequence of the injection will dominate the properties of the injected bunch. Timing can generally be provided much more accurately with optical methods than mechanical manipulation of target properties.

For self-injection some electrons lay constantly in the acceptance of the bubble, defined by the area in phase space in which electrons are trapped by the bubble field and cannot escape. A high temperature of the background plasma can enhance this process as some of the electrons overlap with the trapping separatrix due to their thermal velocity [42,43]. Density transitions in the background plasma can lead to trapping, too, as a widening of the bubble injects electrons into the wake as the plasma wake's phase velocity undergoes a temporal slow down [44–48]. Similarly, the magnetic gradient method acts like a kicker magnet in a conventional accelerator [49].

Short optical methods as colliding laser pulses open the separatrix due to a beat wave in the laser which injects a one-time, narrow electron bunch from the background plasma [50–54].

A stable bubble in a partially ionized gas accepts electrons that are created within. In the related accelerator concept of PWFA, driven by an electron beam, the *Trojan Horse* concept triggers injections in the partially ionized bubble with a laser pulse [55] following with a fixed phase. Variations of this process have been shown experimentally [56,57] and can also be applied to laser driven accelerators with a frequency-doubled ionizing laser [58]. Earlier concepts used ionization in the bubble fields or within the driving laser over time [59–61].

Injecting a pre-accelerated electron bunch into the plasma wake is called *external injection* and is well known in the linear regime of LWFA [62–64].

2. Introduction

3 | PIC Algorithms on Parallel Many-Core Platforms

3.1 PIConGPU

The project PIConGPU [65,66] is an open-source implementation of the fully relativistic PIC algorithm, parallelized over tens of thousands of many-core accelerators. It was published under the GPLv3 together with the library libPMacc (LGPLv3) in August 2013 and is constantly maintained by HZDR together with Center for Information Services and High Performance Computing (ZIH) from TU Dresden. The library libPMacc provides generalized particle-mesh containers and methods for many-core clusters.

The author is one of the core maintainers, being i.a. responsible for new numerical methods (sections 3.2, 3.3), developer coordination and reviews (section 3.4). As part of this diploma thesis the code PIConGPU was further prepared to become a community code in plasma physics.

The strength of the implementation of the PIC algorithms on a parallel many-core architecture is the drastically reduced time to solution for a given setup. Compared to CPU-implementations, simulations that have taken up to three weeks before can now be carried out in less than a day. As a rule of thumb a speed-up of 20 can be achieved with a lower investment in hardware (Eur per Flop/s) and approximately four times higher packing density in computing centers.¹

Previously mentioned challenges in simulations as the artificial growth in emittance and numerical instabilities have been addressed in this diploma

¹Comparison with the 2013/2014 setup of Hypnos (HZDR) [67]: one rack with 68 Nvidia K20x GPUs provides the same peak performance as the other 9 racks of CPU-nodes together.

thesis, e.g. by implementing Lehe’s field solver for the first time on the GPU platform [30]. At the same time new methods, as described in sections 3.2, 3.3, have been developed to extend the overall applicability of the PIC algorithm and to study effects of electron injection in LWFA. Additionally, implementations on the many-core platform have been carried out and published open-source alongside PIconGPU.

3.1.1 GPGPU Architecture and CUDA

Compute Unified Device Architecture (CUDA) provides a C/C++ based programming model for General Purpose Graphics Processing Units (GPGPU) or, more general, many-core hardware [68]. Developed by NVIDIA its primary target platforms are their GPUs, but the general scope of the language makes applications in similar single instruction, multiple data (SIMD) hardware, such as modern x86 processors, possible.² Compared to similar hardware in high-performance computing (HPC) like IBM’s Blue Gene architecture [69], one can see CUDA GPUs as a very dramatic extension of vector units per processing unit.³ The latest GPUs can utilize thousands of CUDA cores with several TFlop/s performance per card.⁴

On the software side, algorithms that perform the exact same transformation on (temporarily) independent data can benefit from significantly improved performance. On the other hand conditional branching at the orders of less than a few dozen threads⁵ leads to an idle GPU rasterization pipeline which prevents efficient concurrent execution.

Parallel Nodes with Many-Core Accelerators

Figure 3.1 shows a common layout of available memory pools and data routing on a heterogeneous node in a cluster. Compared to MPI-parallelized programs that utilize only the CPUs [70], accelerator hardware adds an additional layer of parallelism. Data needs to be transferred over a memory hierarchy with varying latencies and should be stored as close as possible

²See PGI’s CUDA-x86 compiler utilizing SSE/AVX instructions.

³BlueGene/Q: Quad-vector double precision floating point unit “QPX”, Nvidia streaming multi processor “SMX/SMM” 192/128 CUDA cores.

⁴Tesla K40: 12 GB global memory, 2880 CUDA cores, 1.43 TFlop/s theoretical double precision performance, chip set GK110B.

⁵The CUDA architecture is optimized for warps of 32 threads and works most efficient on multiples of these due to caching effects in a block-wise operation mode.

to the respective computing units. Intermediate memory stages like host-side RAM can be used as communication, analysis or I/O cache but lose importance compared to high-bandwidth memory on the accelerator. Recent developments⁶ suggest that next-generation accelerator hardware will have dedicated links for intra-node communication (from and to accelerators, host-RAM or network cards).

Figure 3.1: Common layout of high and low latency memory pools in a single node with accelerator hardware. Routing latencies during the exchange of data can be minimized by explicitly *mapping* accelerators to the closest socket and *pinning* host-RAM.

Codes that utilize the described vectorized hardware efficiently are based on adequate data structures (*data parallelism*, in the next section) and scheduling models (*thread parallelism*).

The latter one should avoid run-time overheads due to branching in `switch/if` operations. For that, programming techniques like C++ template meta-programming can be deployed [73]. Resulting codes are optimized for already known paths of a program at compile-time, e.g. user-specified methods for field solvers or integrators. The resulting code is reusable and orthogonal at the same time as having a very low consumption on registers in the executed kernels. As an example, all fundamental, algorithmic configurations

⁶NVLink [71], Intel Xeon Phi “native” vs. “offload” mode [72].

of PIConGPU are set at compile-time.

Vectorized Data Structures

Optimal utilization of many-core hardware requires to use aligned, vectorized data structures [74]. This section gives an example for such a data type of PIConGPU as it is used in the newly developed algorithms in the following sections.

For reading and writing, aligned data can be transferred with fewer accesses than unaligned data by accessing a whole memory bank at once. In the CUDA architecture the size of a cache line for *global memory* is 128 bytes [68]. Several warps can be coordinated in a *thread block* to access multiples of 128 bytes concurrently.

Figure 3.2: Particle frame lists. Each super cell is associated with a list of frames. Each frame contains a fixed number of attributes and up to n particles. Once in a time step as particles leave and enter a super cell, the frame list is resorted to fill up all but the last frame with particles.

For discretised field data, the grouping of several cells of the PIC algorithm to a *super cell* (see figure 3.5) is feasible. Relocating particle data needs a more complex data structure to be processed.

Figure 3.2 describes the frame list structure in PIConGPU. Each super cell has an associated list of frames that can be expanded/reduced as particles enter/leave. Within a frame up to n particles are stored as a padded *struct-of-arrays* with each attribute consuming $n \cdot x$ bytes with x depending on its type. This scheme allows to operate for all particles concurrently on selected attributes. The number of particles per frame n is simply set as the number of threads in a *thread block*.

3.1.2 The Need for In-Situ Analysis

Over the last decades a distinct problem prevails in high performance computing. One can still argue that Moore's law in terms of a system's Flop/s growth over time remains valid by increasing the number of transistors and cores with heterogeneous systems [75, 76]. Unfortunately, file system performance grows orders of magnitude slower [77].

As an example study on a specific system, figure 3.3 shows an output weak-scaling test performed on a sub-partition of the ORNL Titan supercomputer [78].

Figure 3.3: Parallel file I/O bandwidth for several output strategies over the number of GPU nodes on Titan [79–81].

At the same time the underlying computation of a proportionally increased problem exhibits close-to-ideal scaling behavior [66]. Table 3.1 correlates the two. The effective available bandwidth per Flop/s decreases significantly as the available compute performance increases.

Even if the above comparison does not represent a systematic study over various systems, it illustrates that common problem on today's HPC systems. Attempting to solve that challenge requires a dramatic paradigm change, as simply storing the output of a simulation is going to dominate the overall run-time in the near future.

3. PIC Algorithms on Parallel Many-Core Platforms

# nodes	TFlop/s	BW GiByte/s	Byte/s per MFlop/s
32	13	1.59	125
128	52	5.34	105
512	210	14.94	73
1024	420	19.74	48
4096	1678	45.18	28

Table 3.1: Decrease in the relative output bandwidth with an increase in the number of compute nodes. Exemplary study on a sub-partition of Titan (ORNL). Flop/s performance calculated from measurements and scalings in [66].

Predictions for near-future simulations on HPC systems:

1. Permanent storage of raw data will not be feasible
2. Analysis and result gathering must be done during the computation
3. Reproducibility has to be guaranteed by for repeating simulations

Already the first point seems to violate a very important principle of scientific practice: provability. The sheer impracticability of storing the plain bits of a measurement or simulation in a big parallel hard drive demands for alternative solutions to maintain this principle.

Analysis has to be performed in a staged manner [82] and as close as possible to the volatile memory.⁷ Even checkpoints can benefit from utilizing multi-level memory hierarchies instead of propagating the full simulation state back to a system-wide file system [77].

For exploratory, scientific simulations there comes an additional factor into play compared to a simple parameter study of a fixed problem. While looking for the unexpected it is most often impossible to predict in advance which parameters need to be compared. Exploration and the development of theories is an iterative process and requires to simulate a modified problem set with tunable views on the problem (*online analysis*).

This discussion can be summarized to an important point for scientific programming. As simulations have to be reproducible, the programs that run them must be accessible to be scrutinized. Well documented open source software with the opportunity to participate in the development could enable that. In combination with well described interfaces, common tests and

⁷Or directly in the pipeline of the experiment that “emits” the data.

open data formats communities can be build sharing a common purpose. At the same time post-processing raw data evolves from a standard practice of analysis to a step in development and testing before implementing an in-situ analysis.

The same problem becomes true for very large scale detectors in experiments with billions or trillions of input channels [83]. Similar stages of online data processing can be applied in these facilities, preferring live-analysis for an immediate response over post-processing on already reduced data sets.

3.2 Calculating a 2D Phase Space Distribution

As a part of this diploma thesis a massively parallel analysis of particles was implemented in PIconGPU [66, 84]. The calculation of a two-dimensional phase space distribution is an excellent example of the challenges discussed in section 3.1.2.

As introduced in section 2.3, the general 3D3V PIC algorithm deploys particles in a three-dimensional domain. Each of those particles carries three more degrees of freedom in terms of a momentum vector. For particle accelerators the two-dimensional section of the phase space' *longitudinal momentum* over *direction of acceleration* provides important insight to understand the acceleration mechanism. Alternative representations like the *transverse momentum* over *radius* can hint at driving processes for observables like the beam emittance.

In a classical post-processing chain p -Bytes of data have to be dumped to disk for each particle. Thus, a typical simulation on several ten thousand GPUs with a total of $N = 10^{12}$ makro particles would require to store $\simeq p$ TBytes of raw data for each time step. The two-dimensional phase space on the other hand can be represented by a matrix of $n_{x_i} \cdot n_{p_j}$ pixels each storing 8 Bytes for double precision. Even for very high resolutions of several mega pixels the resulting histogram consumes orders of magnitude less disk space.

Figure 3.4: Reduced network load due to reduction operations in planes of “dimensionality - 1”. Only the marked nodes in (b) perform a collective write to files.

The proposed algorithm for a general heterogeneous architecture starts with

a one-dimensional domain decomposition along the chosen spatial axis of the selected phase space. Adaptions to reduced simulations like 2D3V follow straight forward. For each node of a common plane in figure 3.4a a local phase space distribution is calculated independently. Afterwards the full section S in $r_i^{S[\min, \max]} p_j$ is obtained by a reduce-add operation (figure 3.4b) with logarithmic cost in the number of participating nodes [85]. One can finally exploit the full parallelism of an underlying file system by writing these adjunct pieces, e.g. with MPI-IO [86], to a final file.

The local calculation per GPU has to utilize the typical levels of caching and should use coherent memory access. Therefore a localized number of particles, e.g. within a super cell, is deposited according to their weighting in a spatial subset of the phase space. This matrix has the full number of discretized points in the direction of momentum but only a few number of cells in spatial direction (the length of a corner of the super cell). The scheme is illustrated in figure 3.5. In case that subset does still not fit into a cache local to the processes assigned to that super cell (*shared memory*), the target matrix has to be split up again for sub-ranges in momentum (divide N_p) and particles have to be evaluated multiple times.⁸

Figure 3.5: Binning of the particles per super cell (logical representation, *left*) to the shared section of the phase space (contiguous target matrix, *right*).

⁸Improvement found with René Widera, private communication.

Since several super cells can be calculated concurrently the resulting partial matrix in shared memory must be reduced with atomic operations into the global memory of the GPU before it can be reduced again over the network, as described before.

3.2.1 Applications

Extensive studies for particle accelerators and plasma physics can be carried out with the new implementation on GPGPU hardware. The control and development of new injection methods in LWFA, as presented in chapter 2.4, can benefit directly from that.

In section 2.1.3 the new plugin of PIConGPU was used to illustrate the theory of non-linear wake fields. In combination with the accelerating structure, mainly the bubble fields as in section 2.2.2, direct influence on basic beam properties like maximum charge, emittance and evolution under (non-)conservative force fields can be investigated.

Several numerical studies in chapter 4 have been carried out with the support of the previously described algorithm. As a side topic section 4.3 shows new insights into the dynamics of the relativistic Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability.

3.3 Space Charge Solvers

PIC codes only solve Ampere's and Faraday's law out of the four Maxwell equations. As mentioned in section 2.3, that introduces the need to guarantee the electric and magnetic Gaussian law by appropriate boundary and initial conditions together with a charge conserving current deposition scheme.

Plasma simulations are therefore often initialized with a quasi-neutral start state, placing a compensating number of electrons above the ions of a gas. That ansatz is not suitable to load relativistic charged bunches, e.g for a PWEA. Starting from a neutral source one would need to simulate the whole acceleration process from a cathode to achieve a steady-state of the fields. That steady state shall be the quasi-static approximation, assuming the bunch traveled for an infinite time with constant speed⁹

As a part of this diploma thesis two self-consistent solutions to this issue were found and implemented on a highly parallel many-core architecture.

Preparatory and Related work

A first 2D draft of an explicit scheme was explored by the author during an internship at Instituto Superior Tecnico (Lisbon) in 2012/13 and is not part of this diploma thesis. The derivation of the implicit solver was done by Rémi Lehe (LOA) in 2013/14 [22] based on a dedicated section in a related paper [87]. The work done by the author as part of this diploma thesis concentrates on the general derivation of the n-dimensional explicit scheme. In addition to that the implementation of both schemes and their validation on clusters with accelerator hardware has been carried out.

3.3.1 Previous Schemes

Without a self-consistent solution of the initial fields several work-arounds could be applied. It is possible to initialize a charged particle in a PIC simulation without adding an appropriate charge-compensating second particle. When applying a force or initial momentum to the particle it will create fields that mimic a virtual mirror charge resting at the initial position with an effective infinite mass (figure 3.6).

⁹That assumption works very well for the far-fields of bunch. Nevertheless one should take in mind that the 100% correct near fields are never totally independent of a bunch's origin and will always be influenced by the particle source.

Figure 3.6: Fields according to a second mirror charge build up by solving only Faraday’s and Ampere’s law for an electron bunch initialized with $\gamma_{y,0} = 10$ without self-consistent initial fields. Image created with PIConGPU and IPython [17].

A alternative acceleration scheme implemented in Osiris [88] artificially accelerated the particle over time, building up self-consistent fields. During the acceleration the particle is pushed without feedback from external fields and deposits its current. A similar process implemented by the author increased the charge over time with the advantage of a fixed final position after the acceleration process.¹⁰ Both schemes can be driven with linear, regressive or progressive increase. The limits of these schemes are not all obvious: first of all the self-consistent near-fields take long to build up (empirically, convergence $> \mathcal{O}(\gamma_0)$). In a simulation for a $\gamma_0 \gg 100$ this can easily take several ten thousand time steps. Furthermore from the user side it is very easy to underestimate an appropriate width of the simulation box. Since the transversal electric field of a boosted charged particle is increased with γ the dynamic process of acceleration (as described above) leads to a trailing wing of the orthogonal electric field that can unperceivedly been damped by boundary conditions over time. Since the result of the process will still look qualitatively correct and the charge profiles initialized are usually non-trivial¹¹ it is hard to compare the result with a plain analytical solution.

¹⁰Artificially applying a force to a particle makes a calculation of its final position and the relocation of a target necessary. For moving window simulations the initial speed of the window had to be lowered, too.

¹¹For example a measurement from an experiment.

3.3.2 Solving Poisson's Equation

Initializing the fields correctly from the beginning requires to solve the divergence terms in Maxwell's equations correctly:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \rho / \epsilon_0 \quad (3.1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad . \quad (3.2)$$

It is important to solve the above equations on the correct discretized grid. Since the electric field varies with r^{-2} the field values for cells closest to the origin of a charge can not be solved without taking care of the exact sub-cell distance. For example each component of the Yee scheme has a different position in a cell, see section 2.3.1.

Given a simulation has N cells and P particles one could think of an explicit scheme calculating the precise Lienard-Wiechard fields [89]^(ch. 26)

$$E_x = \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0\sqrt{1-v^2}} \frac{x-vt}{\left[\frac{(x-vt)^2}{1-v^2} + y^2 + z^2\right]^{3/2}} \quad (3.3)$$

$$E_y = \frac{q}{4\pi\epsilon_0\sqrt{1-v^2}} \frac{y}{\left[\frac{(x-vt)^2}{1-v^2} + y^2 + z^2\right]^{3/2}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$E_z \dots \text{similar to } E_y \quad (3.5)$$

$$B_y = -vE_z \quad (3.6)$$

for each particle and field component, making up for $4 \cdot N \cdot P$ function evaluations. Generally speaking there will be much more particles in a simulation than cells $P \gg N$ which makes this algorithm scale with $P \cdot N > N^2$.

It is important to note that one cannot simply evaluate the *analytical* solution for \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{E} of the derived Lienard-Wiechard potentials at the according *discretized* place of the Yee-cell. One can show that this harms the discretized Gaußian law, e.g., $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$. Even for an initialized, resting particle a magnetic field $\mathbf{B} \neq 0$ builds up over time. The particle experiences self-forces, causing it to oscillate around its initial position.

Alternatively one can solve the Lienard-Wiechard potentials analytically, using the *numerical* gradient and curl operator according to the field solvers

stencil to derive the fields:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla^{(+)}\varphi - \partial_t \mathbf{A} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \nabla^{(+)} \times \mathbf{A} \quad (3.8)$$

$$\partial_t := \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \quad . \quad (3.9)$$

The solutions of (3.3) ff. for a point-like particle sitting at the edge of a cell are perfectly symmetric. The stencil of the curl of \mathbf{E} (2.28) has a preferential direction and is not symmetric. Coming back to a resting particle, that means that \mathbf{B} will not stay zero!

The equivalence of analytical and numerical deviations ($\mathbf{B} = 0 \forall t$) is guaranteed by construction using (3.7):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B}^{1/2} &= -\nabla^{(+)} \times \mathbf{E}^0 \cdot \Delta t \\ &= \nabla^{(+)} \times \left(\nabla^{(+)} \varphi \right) \cdot \Delta t \\ &= \left[\frac{(\varphi_{ij+1k+1} - \varphi_{ij+1k}) - (\varphi_{ijk+1} - \varphi_{ijk})}{\Delta y \Delta z} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{(\varphi_{ij+1k+1} - \varphi_{ijk+1}) - (\varphi_{ij+1k} - \varphi_{ijk})}{\Delta y \Delta z} \right] \mathbf{e}_x \\ &\quad + [\dots] \mathbf{e}_y + [\dots] \mathbf{e}_z \\ &= 0 \quad . \end{aligned}$$

The general computational demand is lowered by evaluating the particles assignment shape (section 2.3.2) to the discretized position of the charge per cell. The initial values of the current can be calculated by applying a self-consistent current deposition scheme around the initial time step, e.g. given by Esirkepov [40].

We now assume that the dominating boost occurs along a given axis. A longitudinal energy distribution can simply be initialized by depositing several groups of charges and superposing their created fields.

Figure 3.7: Positions of the discretized fields in a cell_{ij}. The positions of the potentials follow immediately by applying the discretized curl and gradient on (3.7), (3.8) and the continuity equation (for local charge conservation) in Yee's scheme.

In the Lorenz gauge we can now write for the non-homogenous equations:

$$\square\varphi = \epsilon_0^{-1}\rho \quad (3.10)$$

$$\square\mathbf{A} = \mu_0\mathbf{J} \quad (3.11)$$

$$\square := \frac{1}{c^2}\partial_t^2 - \nabla^2 \quad (3.12)$$

Applying the quasi-static approximation now leads again to a Poisson equation:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = -\beta\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \quad (3.13)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \partial_x^2 - \partial_t^2 &= \partial_x^2 - (-\beta\partial_x)^2 \\ &= (1 - \beta)^2\partial_x^2 \\ &= \gamma^{-2}\partial_x^2 \quad (3.14) \end{aligned}$$

With A_x being the only non-zero component of the vector potential:

$$\nabla_*^2 \varphi = -\epsilon_0^{-1} \rho \quad (3.15)$$

$$\nabla_*^2 A_x = -\mu_0 J_x \quad (3.16)$$

$$\nabla_*^2 := \gamma^{-2} \partial_x^2 + \partial_y^2 + \partial_z^2 \quad .$$

3.3.3 Explicit Scheme

In the explicit solver each source term is evaluated via the Lienard-Wiechert potentials for all given grid points.

After a simple Lorentz transformation that is in 3D [89]^(ch. 26)

$$\varphi = \frac{\gamma Q}{\sqrt{\gamma^2 x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \quad (3.17)$$

$$A_x = \frac{p_x Q}{\sqrt{\gamma^2 x^2 + y^2 + z^2}} \quad . \quad (3.18)$$

Yielding for a 2D3V¹² simulation

$$\varphi = \gamma Q \cdot \log(\gamma^2 x^2 + y^2 + z^2) \quad (3.19)$$

$$A_x = p_x Q \cdot \log(\gamma^2 x^2 + y^2 + z^2) \quad . \quad (3.20)$$

A crucial problem arises at divergent points for $x = y = z = 0$ since the charge is defined at the same point as the scalar potential, see figure 3.7. This can be remedied by continuing the potential φ_{ijk} for contributions from a local source ρ_{ijk} in a way that the local numerical source term is valid:

$$-\frac{\rho}{\epsilon_0} \stackrel{!}{=} -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = \nabla_*^2 \varphi \quad (3.21)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= [\varphi_{i+1jk} - 2\varphi_{ijk} + \varphi_{i-1jk}] / \gamma^2 \Delta x^2 \\ &+ \text{y-terms} + \text{z-terms} \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

¹²In a 2D3V PIC simulation particles represent effectively wires with infinite length in the third dimension.

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \text{on-axis symmetry}^{13} \text{ of } \varphi \\ &= \frac{2}{\gamma^2 \Delta x^2} [\varphi_{i\pm 1jk} - \varphi_{ijk}] + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= -2\varphi_{ijk} \cdot \left[\frac{1}{\gamma^2 \Delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{1}{\Delta z^2} \right] \\ &+ 2 \cdot \left[\frac{\varphi_{i\pm 1jk}}{\gamma^2 \Delta x^2} + \frac{\varphi_{ij\pm 1k}}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{\varphi_{ijk\pm 1}}{\Delta z^2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Leftrightarrow \varphi_{ijk} &= \left[\frac{\varphi_{i\pm 1jk}}{\gamma^2 \Delta x^2} + \frac{\varphi_{ij\pm 1k}}{\Delta y^2} + \frac{\varphi_{ijk\pm 1}}{\Delta z^2} + \frac{\rho}{2\epsilon_0} \right] \\ &/ \left[\gamma^{-2} \Delta x^{-2} + \Delta y^{-2} + \Delta z^{-2} \right] . \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

The implementation in PIconGPU iterates over a systolic communication loop as in figure 3.8, distributing the local charge grid points over n nodes. After n communication-and-calculation steps every process has finally calculated the local potentials from the global charge/current grid.

Figure 3.8: Mapping an all-to-all communication on n local one-to-one communications via a systolic loop pattern. The advantage of systolic loops comes with a great reduction of temporary network load by using at the same time short-latency next-neighbor communication. Since the communication-calculation scheme is linearized, the slowest process in the chain will dominate the over all time to solution.

On accelerator hardware like GPUs the available main memory is usually limited to today's 6 to 12GB RAM (CUDA term: global memory). Since

¹³For the values of the vector potential around a central charge the symmetric, on-axis \pm -index terms are equal.

the actual simulation will most likely use most of the memory, storing the additional potential grid for a one-time derivation of the electromagnetic fields might interfere with the possible simulation size that can be handled. One solution for particle-dominated simulations could be to “swap” the particle attributes, after depositing the charge and current values, to the host-side RAM. In the near future dynamic allocation and paging libraries like `mallocMC` [90] can be used for that. Nevertheless, if the memory usage is grid dominated that might again make changes in the distribution over nodes necessary.

The implementation in `PIConGPU` avoids that and uses *mapped memory* [68] to store the local grid of the potentials on the host side memory, accessing it as seldom and as contiguous/aligned as possible. As soon as a local node received a new partial grid from the systolic loop communication a kernel with the explicit calculation is spawned. In this kernel block-wise threads are each dedicated to a specific cell calculating the influence of all charge/current values to that specific point. The advantage of this scheme is that these blocks can read the source grid in big aligned chunks from the accelerators global memory and atomic adds due to superposition can completely avoided. After the block swept over the source grid and the result of the potential has been added up, it is written back via an add over the PCI-express bus to the host-side memory.

The computational demand of that explicit algorithms can not be neglected. Since each grid point can in general carry a non-zero charge value and the potentials have to be evaluated on all N global grid points, the general computational time scales with $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$. Nevertheless, that computation is only performed once at the beginning of a simulation.

3.3.4 Implicit Scheme

As the set of equations (3.15) uses a linear operator operating on a finite-dimensional space, (3.16) can be written as a linear matrix expression [87]

$$\mathbf{M}\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b} \quad . \quad (3.26)$$

The matrix \mathbf{M} is the Laplace stencil which depends on the applied field solver (e.g. Yee). This stencil can be represented by simple function calls

and therefore storing a memory intensive $N \times N$ matrix is not necessary [22]. For instance, a 1D Laplace operator is represented by the following matrix:

$$\mathbf{M}_{ii}^{1D} = \frac{1}{\Delta x^2} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 & \dots \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & \\ \vdots & & & \ddots \end{pmatrix} . \quad (3.27)$$

The vector \mathbf{x} represents the linearized grid points of the potential one wants to solve: φ or $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{x}}$. The source term is represented by \mathbf{b} which is equal to $-\rho/\epsilon_0$ in case of the scalar potential:

$$\mathbf{M}^{(\nabla^2)} \varphi_i = -\rho_i/\epsilon_0 \quad . \quad (3.28)$$

With an appropriate set of boundary conditions the requirements to solve this system of linear equations for \mathbf{x} (φ_i or $\mathbf{A}_{\mathbf{x},i}$) with a conjugate gradient method are fulfilled [22,91]. As given by (3.27) the matrix \mathbf{M} is symmetric, negative definite and real.¹⁴

The complete MPI parallelized algorithm is outlined in appendix B. The calculation of global correction factors α, β and the residuum to check the convergence requires two `MPI_Allreduce` operations per iteration. Besides that, all operations and updates of the temporary fields p, r are, in order of the applied field-solver, next-neighbor local which makes the algorithm very similar to the way one advances the electromagnetic fields in a normal PIC time step.

The GPU implementation uses again mapped memory on the host side to store the temporary values of the potential and auxiliary fields \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{p} . The intermediate value of the operation $\mathbf{M}\mathbf{p}$ is required at two consecutive calculations per loop and efficiently stored in the free memory of the source terms in the GPU's global memory. Next neighbor guard to boarder updates of field \mathbf{p} are efficiently implemented via the libPMacc `GridBuffer` exchange methods. All quasi-local assignment operations are efficiently written by a

¹⁴The conjugate gradient method requires a positive definite matrix. Due to the matrix' symmetry, a transformation of the set of equations (3.26) to $(-\mathbf{M})\mathbf{x} = -\mathbf{b}$ guarantees that [22].

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common kernel `CellwiseOperation` that can be called with various functors to operate on input fields. The reduce operations have been abstracted in `libPMacc` to combine MPI and CUDA reductions even for non-commutative operations like squaring a local cell value and accumulating it via CUDA and MPI.

The conjugate gradient methods requires a maximum of N steps to converge. One could reduce the number of required steps even more by applying a good initial guess for the potential.

3.3.5 Scaling Results on a Cluster With Accelerator Hardware

In addition to the development of the previously described algorithms, the implementation on modern many-core hardware has been carried out. Table 3.2 compares the general properties of both solvers in relation to the global problem size in grid points N .

Poisson Solver	Explicit	Implicit
time to solution	$\mathcal{O}(N^2)$	$\mathcal{O}(N)$
memory consumption	$1N : \varphi/\mathbf{A}_x$	$3N : \varphi/\mathbf{A}_x, r, p$
communication	one all-to-all	$\leq N$ next-neighbor $\leq 2N$ all reduces
pre-conditioner	none	educated guess or zero

Table 3.2: Important characteristics for the two implementations for idealized (serial) hardware without communication/data-access overhead. N is the global number of grid points.

For a simulation the calculation of the initial background fields has to be carried out once at the beginning. A scaling on a parallel machine with n nodes (or GPUs) should study the time to solution with increased number of grid points N . For that reason a *weak scaling* study was performed on the cluster Hypnos (HZDR) [67], increasing the number of total grid points proportionally to the number of GPUs which keeps the local number of cells per GPU constant.

Benchmark results are illustrated in figure 3.9. The scaling indicates that the explicit solver is heavily bound by the time of each local calculation. An increase in n only extends the compute-communication loop in figure 3.8. The implementation of the implicit solver shows effects of communication

and mapped memory overhead. Storing temporary fields on the accelerator-side (in *global memory*) can minimize this influence, but a trade-off should be made between additional memory consumption and run-time.

For 64 GPUs ($134 \cdot 10^6$ cells) the time-to-solution for the implicit method (1 min 56 s) is still orders of magnitude lower than the explicit method (11 h 48 min).

Figure 3.9: Weak-Scaling on Hypnos (HZDR) [67]: The number n of GPUs increases proportionally with the total number of grid cells $N = n \cdot 128^3$. Time to solution for 128^3 cells on 1 GPU: 21 s (implicit) / 664 s (explicit).

3.4 Open-Source Development

The open-source development process with a team of students, post-docs and scientists is highly asynchronous. Due to commitments like studies, conferences, writing final papers, proposals and research one has to regularly synchronize development.

First of all, every participant must be able to start at a defined, stable point from the project. Modern, distributed version control systems like git [92] go one step further. They provide essential support for the important procedure of merging code changes back to the main development *branch*.

Figure 3.10: Example work flow to update the common *mainline* development branch. Colored dots show commits that save a delta to the previous code version. Initially a new branch can be started from any previous commit. After a feature was added, the developer asks for a review (*pull request*). When considered appropriate and correct by other developers, the change set can be merged. Pull requests that significantly diverge from the original branch might make it necessary to rebuild a topic branch via a *rebase* on top of a recent commit from the mainline.

Figure 3.10 illustrates a work flow to update a peer-reviewed open source project like PIconGPU. A developer takes a point of reference (*commit*) and starts working. After some time the new feature or bug fix is considered complete and a review (*pull request*) is proposed for reintegration (*merge*). An active, long-term developer (*maintainer*) is then assigned to act as a coordinating reviewer and gate keeper, while other developers participate in evaluating the change by commenting the pull request.

The qualification as a maintainer is made on objectives like competence on the field of review and experience in the modified part of the code. All de-

velopers agree on a common license for the shared project. Copyleft licenses like the GPL [93] guarantee to be beneficial to the community as they require to share changes at the point of distribution.

Figure 3.11 shows a simplified part of the review process. The user `psychocoderHPC` was assigned as the responsible reviewer while the developer `felix-schmitt-zih` spotted a potential improvement. The author then added an additional commit to the proposed pull-request to satisfy the quality requirements. Each proposed branch and its updates are tested as described in section 3.4.1, allowing the reviewers to concentrate on the content.

Figure 3.11: Code review on GitHub.com (screenshot modified). The timely evolution of the proposed update is shown from top to bottom.

The use of a completely free and permanently open development approach has several advantages. Users of a software have access to releases, new features and at the same time get documented and archived bug fixes. The latter are of great importance for numerical studies since one can directly compare simulations with different versions or even update old versions that contained the same flaw (*backport*). Change logs do not only contain a short note but also reference the description of updates or issues together with the exact patch that had been applied.

The above described work flow distinguishes a project that is developed in an open-source environment and open-source government from one that does not allow interested developers and users to easily participate and regularly have access to current and previous code versions. As mentioned earlier, open source and creative commons licenses approved by the Open Software Foun-

dation (OSF) or respectively Open Knowledge Foundation (OKFN) provide a fundamental environment for that. Furthermore, transparent documentation, open communication,¹⁵ easy following and the possibility to participate are major discriminants. In section 3.1.2 the scientific need for that approach will be picked up again. To the authors knowledge there is only one other code in the plasma physics community that tries to follow similar guide lines (Warp [95]). At the same time PIConGPU reported one order of magnitude more Flop/s performance than any other comparable implementation of the PIC algorithm [66].

3.4.1 Automated Verification of a Particle-in-Cell Code

Continuous integration (CI) is a concept from the domain of software engineering that continuously merges developers' branches with a common *mainline*. The goal is to simplify the integration by checking any incompatibilities already when they are proposed with a change set, increasing stability of concurrent developments.

Figure 3.12: Open source environment for automated tests. Automated tests are triggered for every update of the proposed change set, supporting the manual code review process.

¹⁵Support should be carried out over public issue trackers and open mailing lists. Prevailing “private communication kills the community” [94].

Cooperation on a fairly complex project with people working on various parts of it has several repetitive tasks that can be automated. This is utterly important for the review process described in section 3.4 to support developers and reviewers trying out alternative solutions and improvements.

One design concept of PIConGPU and libPMacc was to use compile-time abstraction as often as possible (see section 3.1). Additionally, fundamental user input errors can already be detected at that point in time. An example is the check for an algorithm's convergence criterion that would otherwise be checked at run-time.¹⁶ Compared to a single run on the target machines, each easily consuming several million CPU-hours, the need to compile the program several minutes on a single node is worth the additional effort.

As a part of this diploma thesis a CI framework has been designed and implemented for PIConGPU. Several compile-time combinations have to be tested during development to see if important combinations are working. Easing the development/testing interplay, several tests can be run in parallel by the compile suite as shown in figure 3.12.

Subsequently to that, the range of plain software testing was extended to a physical platform, making important physical scenarios the benchmark for the correctness of a code. While the last concept is not yet automated completely, the tests themselves are already defined and tested semi-automatically on a regular basis. Preferably, one should take basic plasma properties and well-known plasma phenomena into account to guarantee the validity of simulations in a certain domain.

Implemented tests range from the measurement of the plasma dispersion relation (see section 2.1) over a warm plasma to single-particle trajectories in given electromagnetic fields. Furthermore, the current deposited by macro particles can be verified as well as the according charge conservation of a simulation. Numerical heating for periodic plasma problems is recorded and is one of the properties that is likely to increase with programming errors. The complex plasma dynamics can be verified by measuring growth rates of well known plasma instabilities like the transverse Weibel Instability [96] and the longitudinal Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability [97]. Additional, contributed tests check the radiated spectra of a heads-on Thomson scattering [98].

¹⁶On HPC clusters individual jobs of users are scheduled in a batch system. Usually a fair scheduling algorithm selects the next allocation window for a simulation and waiting queues have to be passed.

4 | Numerical Case Studies

As an application of the new algorithms in chapter 3 selected numerical studies are presented. The first study loads a relativistic electron bunch in a PIC simulation, comparing the self-consistent initial fields from the implemented Poisson solver with the generated fields from a previously used work-around.

The second study is an example of a large-scale, fully relativistic 3D simulation with realistic parameters. A subsequently optimized, down-ramp triggered self-injection in LWFA simulates several millimeters of a gas profile. By separating a distinct part of the profile for injection and a subsequent density plateau for acceleration repeatable, medium-energy electron bunches with a highly correlated energy-time distribution can be generated.

The third study benefits from online visualization and live analysis in petascale simulations. A model of a relativistic plasma instability for the *Gordon Bell* 2013 finale was carried out with PIConGPU reporting the highest peak performance (7.2 PFlop/s) of a PIC simulation up to now [66]. The analysis of its dynamics in phase space can lead to the development of improved diagnostics from emitted radiation into the far field and the control of its occurrence in astrophysical objects and plasma-based particle accelerators.

4.1 Electron Beam Initialization

For the verification of the new beam loading methods in chapter 3.3 a relativistic electron bunch was loaded in a PIC simulation. This is a common starting point for a PWFA setup or a simulation of external injection.

Parameter	Value
$dx = dz$	$0.1 c/\omega_{pe}$
dy	$0.05 c/\omega_{pe}$
dt	$0.04 \omega_{pe}^{-1}$
$\rho(r')$	$r' = r - 0.79 c/\omega_{pe}$
($r' < 0$)	ρ_0
($r' \geq 0$)	0 (homogenous sphere)
$\gamma_{x,0}$	10
particles/cell	8
field solver	Yee
current solver	Esirkepov, TSC shape
boundaries	absorbing, y moving window
# cells 3D3V	$512 \times 512 \times 512$

Table 4.1: Simulation setup for a relativistic particle bunch.

Convenient for testing but *not* required for the new method is the use of a *free-streaming* particle pusher that neglects the feedback of electromagnetic fields on the charged particle bunch. This allows to follow the simply translated initial charge distribution over time which should keep the initial fields constantly co-moving and mainly suppresses numerical beam instabilities (see chapter 2.3).

Figure 4.1 compares the initialization carried out with the implemented Poisson solvers and the work-around that accelerates the particle bunch over 2000 time steps to build up the electromagnetic fields from a simple charge separation. As no difference in the result of the explicit and implicit method was observed both are not differentiated in the plot and just referred to as “Poisson”.

The relativistic electron bunch initialized with a Poisson solver agrees well with the analytical solution in figure 4.1. As the particle bunch is moved constantly the field stays the same even after 2000 time steps. The result of the “acceleration” method differs from the expected result due to the mentioned constraints.

The new methods is less error-prone and has an improved time-to-solution

Figure 4.1: Comparison for a low- γ scenario - fields after 2000 time steps.

over previously applied methods. For the first time, bunch-driven plasma accelerators and injection of relativistic particle bunches in plasma wakefields can be studied with self-consistent fields and modern compute hardware. Future simulations will repeat and improve previously published simulation results based o the new methods.

4.2 Early Down-Ramp Injection

A common issue with density transition triggered injections is its relatively late occurrence in a given gas profile [46]. Using the down-ramp of a Gaussian density profile causes a very uncontrolled injection, see chapter 2.4, lacking strong focusing fields in the low density area of the gas profile (section 2.2.2). A staged approach with a second gas nozzle is hard to realize because of the high emittance of the low-energy beam of the first stage which limits the maximum gap between the nozzles [100].

Previous experiments tried to work around this limitation by laying a razor blade on the exit of a slit gas nozzle [48] creating a relatively sharp peak in density due to the turbulence and shock-front caused thereby. The profile in [48] is characterized by a short sharp edge but ends with a long down-ramp ending into vacuum.

Modified designs with a slit nozzle can create a steep density gradient at the front and a long constant low density area afterwards (figure 4.2). Operating closely below the self-injection threshold of a LWFA a targeted injection can occur at a relatively early down-ramp within the gas profile. Keeping the injected low-energy electrons focused and confined a secondary, lower density stage continues seamlessly. The electron injection is decoupled from a continuous and well controlled acceleration stage with a larger and stable bubble. At the same time, already injected electrons stay within the acceptance of the bubble for the acceleration stage.

Nevertheless the density of the gas profile cannot be controlled in a wide range without changing the gradient in the profile or the relative offset between the two stages. Also adjustments of the position of the razor blade might be necessary which usually interrupts a running experiment.

In cooperation with Eyal Kroupp (Weizmann Institute of Science, Israel) a more stable design for an adjustable two-stage profile was developed in this

Figure 4.2: Phase difference image used for tomography of a slit nozzle. The super-sonic gas jet created a shock front at a razor blade covering part of the exit.¹

¹Courtesy of Alexander Köhler [99]^(fig. 3.3.4)

Figure 4.3: Model for a possible gas profile as in figure 4.2. The area up to 1 mm is modeled by a super-gaussian profile $e^{-10 \cdot (y-1)^4}$ and the down-ramp by an error function $0.25 \cdot \text{erf}[2 \cdot (2 - y)] + 0.75$. ② indicates the area with a density gradient $\partial_x n_e < -0.37/\sqrt{\pi} \cdot n_1/\text{mm}$.

thesis. The proposed experimental realization could use a two-slit nozzle approach as in figure 4.4.

The known minimum steepness of the transition area is given by density-transition injection theory [45]. The presented simulation shows that even a very slowly decreasing density like the given minimum in (compare with figure 4.3) ② down to $\partial_x n_e = -1/\sqrt{\pi} \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}/\text{mm}$ is enough to trigger an injection in a realistic 3D scenario. The length of the constant acceleration stage ③ is limited by depletion, dephasing and the Rayleigh length (due to defocusing) of the laser. Since the bubble expands, the dephasing length must be corrected by a constant offset of the first bucket and roughly corresponds to the maximum plasma intensity n_1 before the down-ramp.

As an idealization the final down-ramp of the gas profile after the low-density plateau in ③ was not considered. It will generally add an additional bunch of low energy, forwards traveling electrons that should be filtered out with bending magnets before analyzing the total bunch charge.

Figure 4.4: Scheme of the double nozzle for the gas injection, experimental realization by Eyal Kroupp. The possibility to control the densities of both slits externally via the applied pressure allows to modify the total density and gradient without breaking the vacuum.

Simulation Parameters

The simulation setup was carried out with PIconGPU, see sections 3.1 and 3.2. Close to the realistic parameters of the Draco laser (HZDR) an in x linear polarized laser with Gaussian beam profile was focused at $y = 1.5$ mm ($z_r = 1$ mm) in the gas profile for a waist size $w_{I,\min}^{(1/e^2)} = 16$ μm with $\lambda_0 = 800$ nm, $a_0 = 4.0$ and $\tau_I^{(\text{FWHM})} = 30$ fs. The maximum gas density $n_1 = 10^{18}$ $\text{cm}^{-3} = 0.57 \cdot 10^{-3} n_c$ was lowered in ② to $n_3 = n_1/2$ with a minimal steepness of $\partial_x^{\max} n_e = -0.23 \cdot 10^{-6} n_c/\lambda_0$. The pre-ionized gas was represented by electrons while neglecting ion motion ($m_p = \infty$). Its modeled profile is described in figure 4.3.

The discretized grid spanned $384 \times 2880 \times 384$ cells with $dy = 32$ nm = $\lambda_0/25$, $dx = dz = 300$ nm = $17.7 c/\omega_{pe}$ and a time step $dt = 0.1$ fs. Initially, one particle per cell represented a weighting of 2880 real electrons per simulated macro electron.

Out of several simulations varying the laser focus position and the density n_1 this simulation showed the best results. On 60 GPUs ($2 \times 15 \times 2$) each simulation took 35.5 h to compute $12 \cdot 10^4$ steps without load balancing.² The run time per simulation includes the output of 0.4 TB over a non-parallel NFS storage with one Object Storing Target (OST).

²Hypnos cluster on a dedicated K20 queue at HZDR

Observations

Figure 4.5: Evolution of the energy histogram for electrons over time. Two clear stages of injection, the major one at the center of the down-ramp $y = 2$ mm, can be identified. The temporally long injection leads to a large energy spread.

Shortly after the start of the down-ramp in ① (figure 4.5) the first set of injections is triggered from the “pile-up” in the wake of the high-density area. In this setup the injected charge at that point carried 47 pC.

As prospected, a strong injection happens around the steepest density gradient at 2.0 mm in the profile ②. Within 600 μm of laser propagation a total charge of 204 pC (figure 4.6) could be loaded into the bubble.

Figure 4.6: Energy distribution in the injected bunches from area ② at $y = 2.74$ mm laser propagation.

4. Numerical Case Studies

The injection stops at the end of the down-ramp letting the injected electrons continuously accelerate in the constant area ③. As seen in figure 4.7 the injected charge is still low enough to avoid transversal beam loading.

Results and Comparison with Previous Publications

Some comparisons can be made to the theory setup published in [45]. The authors used a qualitatively similar density profile in the mildly relativistic regime ($a = 1...2$) with an ultra-short laser pulse. One sees that the minimum density gradient to trigger a down-ramp injection is significantly lower than previously reported in 2D simulations. Due to the long slope, one order of magnitude more charge could be trapped and accelerated. The total energy is in the same order of magnitude while the observed energy spread rather seems to be an effect of the long injection time instead of being caused by space charge effects (which are damped by γ^{-2} in direction of propagation). This could be caused by the use of a more realistic, steadily decreasing gas profile, differences in laser focusing, the increased laser beam energy and/or 3D effects.

The discussed setup shows a promising way to create highly charged bunches with slowly varying density gradients. In the near future, parameter studies in both simulation and experiments will allow to investigate optimal density gradients and density differences.

Figure 4.7: Qualitative evolution of the simulation. The electron injection is triggered in the down-ramp (a), stops after that and injected electrons get further accelerated in (b). As soon as the laser starts defocusing the density profile should be decreased to vacuum and the accelerated charge can be extracted (c).

The presented slowly decreasing down-ramp method is generally applicable to generate short (50 fs), highly charged bunches (204 pC). For applications like betatron radiation sources the high but well correlated energy-time distribution is not a limiting factor. Figure 4.6b shows that the energy distribution is indeed highly correlated with the longitudinal position in the bunch. This should make it possible to extract short bunches during beam transport with a narrow energy spread.

One can expect additional low-energy electrons from a final down-ramp at the end of the gas nozzle and from the second (or later) bubble(s) behind the driver. Both have been neglected for this study.

Nevertheless, applications with a demand for very narrow energy spreads should use electrons injected within a very short time frame. For these, optical injection methods (e.g. colliding lasers, see section 2.4) or external injection with a pre-accelerated electron bunch are promising alternatives.

This example illustrates that realistic simulations including optimization studies can be performed within a few hours with the algorithms for fast PIC simulations implemented in this thesis.

4.3 Phase Space of the Relativistic Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability

The Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability (KHI) is a self-enhancing process occurring at the shear surface of two counter-propagating plasma streams. Following recent publications it is explored as a possible driver for magnetic fields in astrophysical objects such as active galactic nuclei or gamma-ray bursts [97, 101, 102].

Related to plasma-based accelerators, instabilities are of interest because they are known to limit the energy transfer from the driver to the background plasma. Filamentation and shearing instabilities have been observed in plasma wakefield accelerators, inertial confinement fusion and laser-ion acceleration and act in all these applications as a restricting effect³ [96, 103–105]. The knowledge about their appearance, growth rates and the development of control strategies can therefore be highly beneficial across the mentioned areas in plasma physics.

Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
$dx = dy = dz$	$0.06 c/\omega_{pe}$
dt	$0.03 \omega_{pe}^{-1}$
m_{p+}/m_{e-}	1836
$\gamma_{x,0}$	3
particles/cell	8 per species
field solver	Yee
current solver	Esirkepov, TSC shape
filtering	none
boundaries	periodic
# cells 2D3V	8000×1536 (xy /longitudinal)
# cells 2D3V	1536×768 (yz /transversal)
# cells 3D3V	$8000 \times 768 \times 768$

Table 4.2: Parameters for the PIC simulation. The size of the simulation box in x was matched to the period of 9 longitudinal vortices. The size in y direction is set wide enough to an interaction of the two shears.

³in terms of beam break-down, limitation of optimal energy transfer to high density areas of a target's core, filamentation of accelerated ions, etc.

Figure 4.8: Initial orientation of the two counter propagating streams in the simulation. Vortices within the $x - y$ plane describe the *longitudinal* dynamics as the $y - z$ plane represents the *transversal* dynamics.

Parallel to the analysis of a setting presented at *Super Computing 2013* in the finale of the *Gordon Bell prize* [66] the new phase space analysis, introduced in section 3.2, became production ready. The setup (figure 4.8, table 4.2) started with two counter propagating, pre-ionized hydrogen streams in a periodic simulation box with $\gamma_{x,0} = 3$. Along the y -axis the setup is separated in $1/4$ streaming down, $1/2$ up, $1/4$ down as published in [66, 106].

Observations

First results of the analysis of the phase space dynamics of the relativistic KHI are shown in figure 4.11. Compared to previous publications clear details resulting from the unprecedented resolution of the simulation are visible [102].

Electrons from the background plasma penetrate the shear surface due to bending by the magnetic fields therein. Followed by an acceleration to more than twice of their initial momentum as a result of the reduced electron density in this area, creating transversal electric fields from the ion background. Afterwards the electrons are deflected at the opposite side of the stream and tend to stay in its fields. A growing *roll-up* in phase space can be observed over time.

The structure of the magnetic fields and density modulations in the relativistic 3D simulation developed dominantly features of the transversal KHI [106]. This should also be reflected in a signature in phase space.

For a reduced 2D3V setting which studies purely the transversal instability, figure 4.11d shows two significant *wings* to both sides of the growing surface

Figure 4.9: Purely transversal against longitudinal phase space of the relativistic KHI for $t = 46 \omega_{pe}^{-1}$. The second row compares these to the characteristic magnetic field B_z . Images from 2D3V simulations with PIConGPU.

around the initially momentum $\gamma = 3$. The direct comparison confirms that this feature is caused by background electrons that are perturbed by entering the growing volume of the characteristic B_z field structure. While electrons in the purely longitudinal KHI have to pass a short, alternating field (figure 4.9c) and are subsequently drawn into a strong dc-field, electrons in the purely transversal setup (figure 4.9d) can be deflected either inwards or outwards. Depending on the sign of the magnetic field, inwards deflected electrons are again accelerated in the electric field while the outwards moving particles are traveling upfront the growing shear area.

For late times in the evolution of the transversal KHI, the alternating B_z field should lead to a 50% splitting of electrons moving through the intersection $p_y = 0$ with the front of the instability in phase space (figure 4.10). Half the electrons are drawn in the turbulence and half of them pushed upfront of it. A detailed evaluation of the phase space image, using two separated electron species for each shear, is necessary to confirm this speculation. This will be possible by introducing species defined by arbitrary attributes in an upcoming version of PIConGPU.

Figure 4.10: Detail of the transversal phase space (figure 4.9b). Red/green: electrons' origin before mixing.

Implications for Radiation Signatures

The phase space dynamics of the transversal KHI in figure 4.11 are in good agreement with the observations for the full 3D3V evolution. For later analysis, the inner part of the turbulence should provide the clearest signatures as electrons are enforced to oscillate by the strong magnetic fields. Especially in the transverse dominated regime, the electron distribution follows a very narrow and distinct corridor in phase space, thus the derivation of a theory approximating the electrons' trajectories by characteristic electron orbits and deriving emission spectra from these trajectories will be feasible (publication in preparation).

As these diagnostics can now be used for online analysis in full-scale 3D3V PIC simulations on the largest supercomputers currently available, complex plasma effects can be studied in real time without slowing down the computation of the plasma dynamics.

Figure 4.11: Evolution of the phase space of the Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability. The setup used a pre-ionized electron-proton plasma with $\gamma_{x,0} = 3$ for each shear. Images from a 3D simulation with PIconGPU, setup as in [66, 106].

5 | Conclusions and Outlook

In this diploma thesis, a new numerical method to study electron injection for laser-driven particle accelerators was derived. With the generality of the method it is now possible to load relativistic, charged particle bunches with an arbitrary distribution in energy, space and time into running PIC simulations.

For laser-driven electron accelerators this opens new paths to study the injection of electrons self-consistently. Mechanisms like external injection allow to decouple injection and acceleration as a technique to overcome the limits of self-injection in LWFA. With the new scheme, the femtosecond dynamics of external injection can be numerically controlled and varied, allowing to determine optimal parameters such as timing, charge, shape and energy of the injected bunch. Furthermore, studies of beam loading can be performed independently of the injection mechanism by loading particles directly into a plasma wakefield.

With the implementation and verification of a full set of algorithms for the PIC method on GPUs it is possible to reach a new quality in predictive simulations. For the first time, realistic parameter scans can be varied over a broad range of initial conditions in a simulation's time-to-solution short enough to allow estimates of stochastic errors of a setup. Simulations requiring a few hours of computing time instead of several weeks can furthermore take systematic variations from several solvers into account. Advanced field solvers such as the method of Lehe have been ported to GPUs in this thesis to suppress numerical artifacts like the numerical Cherenkov noise in simulations.

As realistic, atomic models gain importance in PIC simulations, the underlying power of the many-core hardware enables future developers to include additional fundamental processes such as improved ionization and collision

5. Conclusions and Outlook

schemes. The introduction of PIConGPU to the open source community provided the necessary long-term strategy to improve accelerator research with a reliable, documented, enhanceable and verifiable code.

A challenge in high-data rate experiments and HPC stands with the impossibility to continue to store high-bandwidth, parallel streams of raw data to permanent storage for post-processing. The strategy proposed and followed in this diploma thesis relies on massively parallel, live analysis of raw data instead of filtering and thus losing information. With that it is not only possible to handle the amount of data but also to introduce a new quality in studies. Since the important parameters can be processed *in-situ* as the simulation is still running, explorative real-time interaction with a setup of interest is now feasible.

As an example, a highly parallel calculation of a two-dimensional phase space section was implemented in PIConGPU. For a realistic simulation of the injection dynamics of a LWFA this analysis alone can reduce the output of a simulation by more than three orders of magnitude while providing an instantaneous feedback on the acceleration process before the simulation even ended.

Finally, several numerical case studies have been carried out as a starting point for further investigations. It has been indicated that down-ramp triggered self-injection is difficult to scale to multi-GeV, narrow peak electron accelerators as the timing sequence of injection translates into a final energy spread. Nevertheless, they can provide bunches with moderate charge and a distinct energy-time distribution. For applications where the total energy spread is not a limiting parameter and for setups of several acceleration stages this mechanism can possibly provide reliable medium-energy bunches. The application of the PIC method and the power of a many-core accelerator implementation was demonstrated with a simulation of the relativistic Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability during this diploma thesis. With that the author participated in the Gordon Bell finale, an Association for Computing Machinery (ACM) award recognizing outstanding achievements in high-performance computing in November, 2013 (for further results, see [66,106]). A subsequent analysis performed in this diploma thesis could furthermore determine characteristic features for the dominance of the transversal or respectively the longitudinal constituent of the plasma instability. In future research one can continue to associate these effects with related signatures in

emitted far field spectra, allowing to prove the appearance of the instability in far-away astrophysical objects and laser-plasma experiments.

5. Conclusions and Outlook

Appendices

A | Dispersion Relation of the Yee Solver

The discretized wave equation in Yee's scheme is given by formula (2.29). Since arbitrary waves can be composed by a sum of (an infinite number of) plain waves, we exemplarily analyze the dispersion of a plain electric wave in vacuum:

$$\mathbf{E}_{ijk}^n = \mathbf{E}_0 \cdot e^{i(\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega n \Delta t)} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{r} = \begin{pmatrix} i \cdot \Delta x \\ j \cdot \Delta y \\ k \cdot \Delta z \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\stackrel{1D}{\Rightarrow} \mathbf{E} = E_{x,i}^n = E_0 \cdot e^{i(ki\Delta x - \omega n \Delta t)} \quad . \quad (2)$$

Entered in (2.29) the left-hand side (second derivative in time) results in:

$$\frac{\mathbf{E}_0 \cdot e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \cdot \{e^{-i\omega(n-1)\Delta t} - 2e^{-i\omega n \Delta t} + e^{-i\omega(n+1)\Delta t}\}}{(c\Delta t)^2} = \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{E}_0 \cdot e^{i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - i\omega n \Delta t} \cdot \{e^{+i\omega \Delta t} - 2 + e^{-i\omega \Delta t}\}}{(c\Delta t)^2} = -\frac{\mathbf{E}_i^n \cdot 4 \sin^2(\omega \Delta t / 2)}{(c\Delta t)^2}$$

and the right-hand side (exemplary for the second derivative in x):

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{E_0 \cdot e^{-i\omega n \Delta t} \cdot \{e^{ik_x(i-1)\Delta x} - 2e^{ik_x i \Delta x} + e^{ik_x(i+1)\Delta x}\}}{(\Delta x)^2} &= \quad (4) \\ \frac{E_0 \cdot e^{-i\omega n \Delta t + ik_x i \Delta x} \cdot \{e^{-ik_x \Delta x} - 2 + e^{ik_x \Delta x}\}}{(\Delta x)^2} &= -\frac{E_{x,i}^n \cdot 4 \sin^2(k_x \Delta x/2)}{(\Delta x)^2} \end{aligned}$$

So the dispersion relation $\omega(k)$ in Yee's scheme for electromagnetic waves is:

$$\frac{\sin^2(\omega \Delta t/2)}{(c \Delta t)^2} = \sum_{r=\{x,y,z\}} \frac{\sin^2(k_r \Delta r/2)}{(\Delta r)^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\stackrel{1D}{\Rightarrow} \sin(\omega \Delta t/2) = \pm \frac{c \Delta t}{\Delta x} \cdot \sin(k_x \Delta x/2) \quad . \quad (6)$$

We derive the phase and group velocity for various frequencies on the grid by:

$$v_\phi(k_x) = \frac{\omega}{k} = \frac{2}{\Delta t \cdot k_x} \cdot \arcsin \left\{ \frac{c \Delta t}{\Delta x} \sin(k_x \Delta x/2) \right\} \quad (7)$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{k_x \Delta x/2 \ll 1} v_\phi(k_x) = c \quad (8)$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow (\Delta x/c)^-} v_\phi(k_x) = c \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_{\text{group}}(k_x) &= \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial k} = \frac{\partial}{\partial k} \left[\frac{2}{\Delta t} \cdot \arcsin \left\{ \frac{c \Delta t}{\Delta x} \sin(k_x \Delta x/2) \right\} \right] \\ &= \frac{c \cdot \cos(k_x \Delta x/2)}{\sqrt{1 - \left\{ \frac{c \Delta t}{\Delta x} \cdot \sin(k_x \Delta x/2) \right\}^2}} \quad (10) \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{k_x \Delta x/2 \ll 1} v_{\text{group}}(k_x) = c \quad (11)$$

$$\Rightarrow \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow (\Delta x/c)^-} v_{\text{group}}(k_x) = c \quad . \quad (12)$$

B | MPI Parallelized Conjugate Gradient Algorithm

In order to solve the system of linear equations given by (3.26) with a conjugate gradient method two auxiliary scalar fields have to be allocated

$$\mathbf{p}, \mathbf{r} \in \mathbb{R}^N \quad (13)$$

$$\epsilon^{(q),(q-1)}, \alpha, \beta, pMp \in \mathbb{R} \quad (14)$$

with N being the number of grid points in the simulation (independent of its dimensionality). These fields can be allocated in the same spatial domain decomposition as the source terms (charge and current).

Their initial values are set to

$$\mathbf{r}^{(0)} = -\rho/\epsilon_0 (-\mathbf{M}\varphi^{(0)}) \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{p}^{(0)} = \mathbf{r}^{(0)} \quad (16)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon &= \mathbf{r}^T \mathbf{r} \\ &= \sum_{ijk} r_{ijk}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

while an appropriate guess for $\varphi^0 = 0$ is possible. The superscript (q) in brackets denotes the iteration q . The subscript can be linearized to a one-dimensional index. For the sake of recognition the example is carried out with a three-dimensional index ijk and for the scalar potential.

To calculate the scalar value ϵ one has to calculate, reduce and broadcast the cell-local value of (17) for each node. The calculation can be done inde-

pendently on each subset (node) and the result requires an `MPI_Allreduce` (`MPI_SUM`).

The main loop of the implicit solver iterates over steps q (if not denoted, the variables value is for step q):

$$\Rightarrow \text{copy neighboring cells of } \mathbf{p} \text{ with ghost/guard layer width } \mathcal{O}(\nabla \times \epsilon) \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} pMp &= \mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{M} \mathbf{p} \\ (\text{Yee}) &= \sum_{ijk} p_{ijk} \left[(p_{i+1jk} - 2p_{ijk} + p_{i-1jk}) / (\gamma \Delta x)^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (p_{ij+1k} - 2p_{ijk} + p_{ij-1k}) / (\Delta y)^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (p_{ijk+1} - 2p_{ijk} + p_{ijk-1}) / (\Delta z)^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{MPI_Allreduce(MPI_SUM) of } pMp \quad (20)$$

$$\alpha = \epsilon / pMp \quad (21)$$

$$\varphi += \alpha \cdot \mathbf{p} \quad (22)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \varphi_{ijk} += \alpha \cdot p_{ijk}$$

$$\mathbf{r} -= \alpha \cdot (\mathbf{M} \mathbf{p}) \quad (23)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow r_{ijk} -= \alpha \cdot [\text{see stencil terms right in (19)}]$$

$$\epsilon^{(q)} = \sum_{ijk} r_{ijk}^2 \quad \text{see (17)} \quad (24)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{MPI_Allreduce(MPI_SUM) of } \epsilon^{(q)} \quad (25)$$

$$\beta = \epsilon^{(q)} / \epsilon^{(q-1)} \quad (26)$$

$$\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{r} + \beta \cdot \mathbf{p} \quad (27)$$

$$\Leftrightarrow p_{ijk} = r_{ijk} + \beta \cdot p_{ijk} \quad .$$

One can abort the loop as soon as $\epsilon^{(q)}$ becomes sufficiently small. Eventually the values of φ will converge to the solution of the system in $q \leq N$ steps. For a realistic load balancing and “enough” memory per node the `MPI_Allreduce` operations of single scalar values should not dominate the overall computational performance. Using a more sophisticated initial guess for $\varphi^{(0)}$ and consequently $\mathbf{r}^{(0)}$ can reduce the number of iterations tremendously.

Acronyms

CFL Courant-Friedrichs-Lewy. 22, 24

CI Continuous integration. 56, 57

CPA chirped pulse amplification. 12

CUDA Compute Unified Device Architecture. 34, 36

GPGPU General Purpose Graphics Processing Units. 34, 42

GPU Graphics Processing Units. 20, 24, 26, 34, 37, 40–42, 49, 51–53, 64

HPC high-performance computing. 34, 37, 38, 57, 74

HZDR Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden - Rossendorf. xxi, xxxix, 16, 33, 52, 53, 64

KHI Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability. xix, xxii, 68–71

LWFA Laser-Wakefield Acceleration/Accelerator. xxi, 12, 15, 16, 20, 23, 24, 28–31, 34, 42, 59, 62, 73, 74

OKFN Open Knowledge Foundation. 56

OSF Open Software Foundation. 55

OST Object Storing Target. 64

P³M Particle-Particle-Particle-Mesh. 27

PIC Particle-in-Cell. 14, 15, 20, 21, 24, 25, 27, 29, 33, 34, 36, 40, 43, 48, 51, 56, 59, 60, 67, 71, 73, 74

Acronyms

PM Particle-Mesh. 25

PWFA Plasma-Wakefield Acceleration/Accelerator. 29, 31, 43, 60

SIMD single instruction, multiple data. 34

ZIH Center for Information Services and High Performance Computing. 33

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Publications of the Author

During the time of this Diploma thesis, the author published and authored the following publications and scientific talks:

Peer Reviewed Papers

- M. Bussmann, A. Huebl et al. “*Radiative signatures of the relativistic Kelvin-Helmholtz instability*,” Proceedings of SC’13: International Conference for High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, ACM 2013, doi:10.1145/2503210.2504564, ISBN:978-1-4503-2378-9
- A. Huebl et al. “*Visualizing the Radiation of the Kelvin-Helmholtz Instability*,” 7th Triennial Special Issue of the IEEE Transactions on Plasma Science, Images in Plasma Science, 2014, doi:10.1109/TPS.2014.2327392, arXiv:1404.2507

Conferences and Invited Talks

- “*PICongPU - Ultrafast OpenSource Plasma Physics*,” Weizmann Institute of Science, Tel Aviv, October 23th, 2013
- “*Loaded and Unlocked - Accelerating OpenSource Plasma Physics*,” Laboratoire d’Optique Appliquée, Paris, January, 2014
- “*Unleashing PFlop/s for Plasma Science with PICongPU*,” DPG Spring Meeting, Berlin, March 21th, 2014
- “*Scaling Plasma Simulations to more than 18,000 GPUs*,” Workshop Programming of Heterogeneous Systems in Physics, Jena, July 15th, 2014

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Erklärung

Hiermit versichere ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit ohne unzulässige Hilfe Dritter und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Die aus fremden Quellen direkt oder indirekt übernommenen Gedanken sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die Arbeit wurde bisher weder im Inland noch im Ausland in gleicher oder ähnlicher Form einer anderen Prüfungsbehörde vorgelegt.

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